

Review of existing and emerging techniques for benthic habitats

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List of abbreviations

Term	Explanation
AAM	Active Acoustics Methods
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
AZFP	Acoustic Zooplankton Fish Profiler
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CDOM	Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter
CS	Citizen Science
CTD	Conductivity-Temperature-Depth
ddPCR	Digital Droplet PCR
DIDSON	Dual-Frequency Identification Sonar
dPCR	Digital PCR
DVL	Doppler Velocity Logs
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variables
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
EOV	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
FCM	Flow Cytometry
FIM	Flow Imaging Microscopy
GLS	Geolocation System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
HSI	Hyperspectral Imaging
MBB	Marine Biology and marine Biodiversity
MBES	Multibeam Echosounder
MFLS	Multibeam Forward-Looking Sonar
ML	Machine Learning
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSI	Multispectral Imaging
NIS	Non-indigenous species
OBIA	Object-Based Image Analysis
OCROV	Observation Class ROV
ODM	Open Drone Map
PAM	Passive Acoustics Methods
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
qPCR	Quantitative PCR
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RGB	Red-Green-Blue colour bands

ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
SAV	Submerged Aquatic Vegetation
SB-AGDS	Single-Beam Acoustic Ground Discrimination Systems
SfM	Structure-from-Motion
SLAM	Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping
SSS	Sidescan Sonar System
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TDR	Time-Depth Recorder
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UAV	Uncrewed/Unoccupied/Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
USBL	Ultra Short Baseline
USV	Uncrewed/Unoccupied/Unmanned Surface Vehicle
VHF	Very High Frequency
VHR	Very High Resolution
VTOL	Vertical Take-off and Landing (UAV)
WFD	Water Framework Directive
AAM	Active Acoustics Methods

Executive summary

There is an urgent need for accurate and cost-efficient techniques and methodologies to map and monitor European coastal ecosystems. This to ensure a solid foundation for implementing the policies that aims for reaching good environmental status, safeguarding biodiversity, and mitigate impacts of anthropogenic pressures. This review includes both platforms and their appurtenant methods including satellites, drones and aerial platforms, remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), moorings, cabled observatories, and landers, flow cytometry (FCM) and flow imaging microscopy, photogrammetry and drop videos, acoustics, eDNA, biologging, and citizen science. The use of each technique was specifically assessed in terms of monitoring and mapping of benthic habitats including demersal fish, benthic fauna, corals, seagrass, macroalgae and other aquatic vegetation, as well as benthic microorganisms. The review also includes seabirds. The catalogue on technologies includes descriptions of each technology, as well as descriptions of strengths and weaknesses together with an assessment of the technology readiness level. We describe how the technologies are currently used for monitoring and what kind of example cases are available based on literature. The Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) that could benefit from the type of data collected using each technology are also listed. Finally, we summarise key aspects of the technologies and highlight that leveraging multiple complementary approaches is crucial for comprehensive understanding and monitoring of marine benthic habitats.

Emerging technologies for benthic observations

As was highlighted in the OBAMA-NEXT project application; *the marine environment in Europe is governed by several EU directives including the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Water Framework Directive and the Birds and Habitats Directives, and their national equivalents in Norway and the UK. Successful implementation of these directives requires accurate mapping and monitoring of changes in a broad range of physical, chemical, and biological components. This information is required to assess and track the health of marine species and ecosystems, identify pressures and establish evidence-based measures to reduce them and to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented management actions. However, this is currently hampered by insufficient, unadopted and/or missing information in the form of e.g., lack of spatial and temporal coverage, suitable measurement parameters and observations on some important ecosystem components. These limitations hinder our capacity to monitor marine ecosystems, understand the complex linkages between human pressures and ecosystem responses and develop and evaluate policies for the sustainable use and management of marine resources.*

Integrated ocean observations are needed to understand how marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning change in response to human pressures and climate change and to develop and implement appropriate policies and management approaches (Locatelli, 2016; Smale et al., 2019; Chust et al., 2022). Today, biological observations gathered using traditional in situ monitoring programmes are costly and provide information with relatively limited spatial coverage and temporal resolution. Furthermore, many traditional techniques rely on the knowledge of experts, potentially resulting in person-to-person biases giving rise to inconsistencies over time and between areas. For example, observations of benthic vegetation are typically performed by video-inspection from underwater cameras or divers, introducing significant variability in the observations (Balsby et al., 2013). Moreover, fewer people today are trained with sufficient taxonomical skills (Britz et al., 2020), challenging the future of traditional biological monitoring programmes. New technologies for obtaining biological observations have emerged in recent years, but their consolidation in marine monitoring, in this case benthic habitat mapping is still lacking. Consequently, there is an urgent need to integrate emerging technologies into marine monitoring programmes to overcome these limitations (Borja and Elliott, 2021).

New techniques that can be applied to monitoring of benthic habitats are emerging at an increasing rate (Figure 1). Many of the methods bring with them the potential of gathering novel data types and providing higher spatial and temporal resolution of data. The choice of methodologies varies depending on which part of the marine benthic system they target (e.g. the shallow photic littoral zone vs the deeper aphotic zone), the questions being addressed (e.g. biodiversity assessment, invasive species, carbon cycling) and whether habitats or specific species are being investigated. Species characteristics such as their size, motility and lifespan will also affect the methodological choices.

Figure 1. The number of scientific publications referencing novel techniques for monitoring marine benthic systems has exploded over the recent decade. Results are based on a search using the key words benthic and monitoring combined with technology specific key words on Web of Science. The “benthic” keyword was not used for biologging since that was used for birds in the context of this document.

This document describes a wide range of technologies, together with platforms, applied in the monitoring of marine benthic systems. Its intention is to provide relevant background information for planning future monitoring activities and choosing the most appropriate methods to target the research and assessment aims of interest. The catalogue includes information on both emerging and existing technologies with emphasis on their use for monitoring of benthic habitats and biodiversity. Since some of the technologies originate from or are also applied in pelagic habitats, some of the references are pelagic. The catalogue contains a brief description of each technique and highlights strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and risks of each approach, as well as examples on how the method can be applied to monitoring, and a description of the technology readiness level (TRL). Additionally, we list the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) that could benefit from the type of data gathered using each technique (Muller-Karger et al., 2018).

Setting the scope for the review

The aim of deliverable D3.1 is to review existing and emerging techniques for observations of benthic marine systems, including flora, fauna and microorganisms from soft- and hard-substrata. Special emphasis has been put on methods that could be used for monitoring and mapping of biodiversity. The focus is on benthic habitats including demersal fish, benthic fauna, corals, seagrass, macroalgae and other aquatic vegetation, as well as benthic microorganisms (Figure 2). In addition to benthic species, the review also includes seabirds. Birds are included in WP3 since methods used for observing seabirds are more related to benthic than pelagic technologies. The focal technologies include both platforms and their appurtenant methods, i.e., satellites, drones and aerial platforms, remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), moorings, cabled observatories and landers, flow cytometry (FCM) and flow imaging microscopy, photogrammetry and drop videos, acoustics, eDNA, biologging, and citizen science. The review of the technologies and their application to benthic habitats and sea birds was conducted by examining scientific literature, projects, and descriptions of monitoring programmes. Each technique is described in its own section including an overview, monitoring applications and examples, assessment of technology readiness level (TRL) as well as an assessment of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT).

Figure 2. Organisms targeted in the report from left to right: corals, macroalgae and other aquatic vegetation, benthic fauna, benthic reefforming habitats, sediment dwelling micro-organisms, demersal fish, seabirds (icons by Science Crunchers).

Description

Each section includes a description of the technology and appurtenant methods including a general description of the method, information on what the technology is used for, and information on data processing needed to achieve relevant data products. Each section also highlights examples of how the methods have been applied to monitoring or mapping, in particular cases that have been or can be applied to the monitoring of the extent and ecological condition of habitats, biodiversity, as well as the evaluation of carbon stocks or sequestration. Several information products under development in OBAMA-NEXT, and described in Borja et al., (2023), use data collected using technologies presently reviewed in this document.

Essential Biodiversity Variables and Essential Ocean Variables

To assess the overall health of oceans across multiple platforms the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) panels for experts have identified Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs). The variables have been chosen by their impact and feasibility for monitoring purposes and help interpret connections between ocean and other climate systems such as the atmosphere. Similarly, Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) can also be used for monitoring biodiversity in marine ecosystems. Monitoring biodiversity is a good indicator for change in ocean health, but systematic observations are needed, and different methods like *in situ* and remote sensing need to be aggregated to create an overall picture. The information about change is important for policy making and combined with social and economic information it can be used to identify responses to pressures.

Technology readiness level

The TRL describes the current stage of a technology. As TRL can be evaluated for different purposes, the TRL in the present work has been evaluated in terms of readiness for monitoring of biodiversity. As such, some of the included technologies can have higher technology readiness in other contexts and applications. The highest level was only granted if the technology to our knowledge is currently applied in official monitoring. A description of the different TRLs is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the technology readiness levels (TRLs) as defined by the European Commission (2014)

Technology readiness level	Description
TRL 1	Basic principles observed
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept
TRL 4	Technology validated in lab
TRL 5	Technology validated in relevant environment
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL 8	System complete and qualified
TRL 9	Actual system proven in operational environment

SWOT-table

Information for each technology is assessed based on a strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) approach in terms of how each technique can support and contribute to existing monitoring. The strengths will highlight aspects of the method such as spatial and temporal scale, possibilities for automation, cost-efficiency, etc. The weaknesses will include descriptions on weaknesses of the approach, such as uncertainties with the method, dependencies on weather conditions, etc. The opportunities section will

highlight opportunities specifically considering use in monitoring. The threats category will highlight, for instance, if the implementation of the method could have negative effects on other monitoring efforts.

Catalogue on existing and emerging technologies

The following section consists of the catalogue of technologies. At the start of each section the targeted organisms are depicted with dark colour.

Satellites

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Method description

Satellite earth observation (EO) may be seen to have started with the Landsat program in 1970s, the first non-militaristic EO program. Since, the program has provided continuous observations with a series of satellites. It has later been accompanied by several other EO satellite missions, both from the public sector such as the European Space Agency's (ESA) Copernicus program with its Sentinel satellites, and private companies. Though the satellite missions are largely focused for monitoring land cover, their applicability to marine benthic habitat mapping has been successfully demonstrated by using the long time series of the Landsat program for kelp forest and seagrass change detection (Bell et al., 2020; Pu et al., 2012), as well as in mapping studies over various benthic habitats in different water conditions with the newer higher resolution sensors (e.g. Coffey et al., 2023; Kuhwald et al., 2022; Lyons et al., 2015; Poursanidis et al., 2021; Traganos et al., 2022; Wilson et al., 2022).

Optical sensors on board the satellites can be roughly split to multispectral (MSI) and hyperspectral instruments (HSI). The main difference is that the MSI sensors record reflected solar radiance in few bands with wider wavelength ranges across the electromagnetic spectrum, whereas HSI capture detailed spectrum in numerous (tens to hundreds) bands of narrow wavelength ranges, which may be used for finer scale spectral separation between species groups or species. Spatial, spectral, temporal, and radiometric resolution of satellite sensors vary by the sensor onboard, and by satellites (Table 2). In general, there is a trade-off between the area that is covered, the pixel resolution, and at what level of spectral detail the instrument can measure. Satellites with coarser spatial resolution (Sentinel-2 (S2), Landsat 8/9) can map large areas but don't have the same level of spatial detail that can be acquired via very high resolution (VHR) MSI satellite imagery, or the spectral details from HSI. Temporally, S2 and Landsat 8/9 satellites have a constant revisit time (5 and 8

days at the equator, respectively), whereas VHR satellites, such as Planet Dove, Pleiades Neo, etc. may be tasked for an area even several times a day depending on the satellite and constellation.

Table 2. Examples of multi and hyperspectral satellite resolutions. The list is non-exhaustive and only aims to illustrate key differences between sensors. Sensor type abbreviations: PAN – panchromatic, MSI – multispectral, HSI – hyperspectral instrument. Table information collected from eoportal.org (last accessed 12.4.2024).

Satellite	Spatial resolution (m) and instrument type	Spectral range	Revisit time	Swath width (km)	Operational since	Agency
Sentinel-2 A/B	10-60 (MSI)	443 – 2400 nm in 13 bands	10 days for single satellite, 5 days between S2A/S2B	290	2015/2017	ESA
Landsat 8/9, OLI instrument	15 (PAN), 30-60 (MSI)	443 – 2200 nm in 9 bands	16 days for single satellite, 8 days between Landsat 8/9	185	2013/2021	NASA
WorldView-2	0.5 (PAN), 2 (MSI)	450 – 800 nm in 8 bands	Once a day	16.4	2009	DigitalGlobe, Maxar
Pleiades 1A/1B	0.5 (PAN), 2 (MSI)	450 – 820 nm in 4 bands	Once a day	20	2011/2012	CNES, Airbus
Pleiades Neo	0.3 (PAN), 1.2 (MSI)	400 – 880 nm in 6 bands	Two times a day	14	2021	Airbus
Planet Dove*	3.7 (MSI)	420 – 860 nm in 4 bands	Several times a day	-	2018	Planet
EO-1, Hyperion instrument	30 (HSI)	400 - 2500 nm in 220 bands	16 days	7.5	2000-2017	NASA

*Multiple different generation sensors are included in Planet constellation

Satellite images can be acquired at different processing levels, varying from unprocessed (Level 1) images to fully pre-processed images. Pre-processing of satellite images consists of multiple steps which results in images ready for analysis. Users may usually download images, which have already been through initial processing steps, such as calibration of raw data to radiances and geometric correction. Atmospheric correction is often performed in benthic mapping studies to remove the effect of atmosphere and to separate the relatively low proportion of water leaving radiance from the total radiance recorded by the sensor. Further processing may include sun glint removal (Hedley et al., 2005) to reduce the effect of specular reflection of sunlight towards the sensor from the water surface, and water column correction (Lee et al., 1994; Maritorena et al., 1994) to account for attenuation of light in the water column and to retrieve reflectance at the sea bottom. However, depending on the atmospheric conditions and optical properties of water, these algorithms may perform with variable results (Eugenio et al., 2017; Vahtmäe et al., 2021; Warren et al., 2019).

Field observations collected by traditional methods (such as diving and underwater videos) are often used as ground truth data in creating training dataset for supervised satellite image classification. Machine learning (ML) algorithms are nowadays widely used in classification tasks to assign the spectral reflectance values of satellite image to benthic habitat classes (Misiuk and Brown, 2023). Object-based image analysis (OBIA)

(Blaschke, 2010), where similar pixels are grouped into ‘objects’ which are then classified based on statistics computed from pixels within the object instead of classifying single pixels, have increased during the last decade, and shown improved capability differentiating benthic habitats (Kutser et al., 2020). Most recently, deep learning (DL) based classifiers have also been demonstrated in benthic mapping (Coffer et al., 2023).

Applications to monitoring

Satellite based mapping may be used to quantify extents of various habitats such as coral reefs (e.g. Lyons et al., 2015; Purkis et al., 2019), seagrasses (e.g. Coffer et al., 2023; Pu et al., 2012; Traganos et al., 2022; Wilson et al., 2019) and macroalgae (e.g. Bell et al., 2020; Houskeeper et al., 2022), and change in them. Further, the coverage maps may be converted to biomass estimates, if relationship between percentage cover and biomass can be shown and modelled (Bell et al., 2020; Roelfsema et al., 2014; Vahtmäe et al., 2021). Allen Coral Atlas (allencoralatlas.org) and Kelp Watch (kelpwatch.org) show browser interface examples of satellite-based monitoring programs.

Technology readiness level

Satellite images are widely used in mapping studies (Kutser et al., 2020; Misiuk and Brown, 2023), and they have been successfully applied in creating monitoring programmes. Cloud computing, with openly available satellite image archives (S2 and Landsat), joined with machine learning enable efficient processing of large datasets, and thus allow the creation of automated processing pipelines for mapping and monitoring of large areas. Allen Coral Atlas and Kelp Watch demonstrate that the TRL for multispectral satellite remote sensing has reached TRL 9 in some applications. Coffer et al. (2023) tested a framework for VHR image-based monitoring of seagrasses on continental scale, which suggests TRL 7 for this method. Hyperspectral satellite remote sensing has been showcased in benthic mapping (Pu et al., 2012), but its use on a larger scale has been limited. This is likely due to fewer satellites with hyperspectral instruments, the more limited area that can be mapped in a single satellite overpass, and heavier data load and computational requirements in processing. Thus, hyperspectral satellite remote sensing is estimated to have TRL 6.

To conclude, satellite remote sensing is well established in benthic monitoring, but combining imagery from different sensors and platforms to monitoring workflows, development in future satellite missions and hyperspectral satellites, and using various data sources with ML and AI tools leave room for development of new applications in benthic monitoring.

EBVs and EOVs

Satellites can provide valuable indirect information related to benthic EOVs and EBVs through about benthic habitats, including coral reefs, seagrass beds, and rocky substrates. Satellites can provide information about bathymetry of the sea floor, which is crucial for understanding benthic habitat distribution. Data products

derived from satellite images are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 3 and 4.

Table 3. EBVs that can be addressed by satellite-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Species traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phenology
Ecosystem functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary productivity - Ecosystem phenology - Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 4. EOVs that can be addressed by satellite-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat extent - Global geographical distribution - Essential fish habitat extent
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent of seagrass meadows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global and regional seagrass distribution - Essential fish habitat extent - Seagrass habitat fragmentation - Contributions to blue carbon storage
Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of coral cover and areal extent
Mangrove cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mangrove fringe width and area 	

Technology SWOT: satellites

Strengths	Weaknesses
Large scale coverage: Mapping areal extents from local to global scales	Limited by water optical depth. Challenging in optically complex waters Some have limited spatial resolution
Open data available	Multispectral instruments mainly applicable for species group level mapping
Cost effective	Weather dependent Clouds, waves and specular reflection of sunlight towards the sensor from water surface (sun glints) decrease the amount of usable imagery
Time series analysis and change and trend detection in habitat extent over years	Generally, targets broader habitats with low taxonomic resolution Data volume associated with HSI satellites
Opportunities	Threats
Repeatable large-scale global monitoring Advancements in sensor technology that could improve benthic mapping	Underestimation if habitat extent beyond water optical depth is not accounted for
Cloud processing	Mixed classification between spectrally similar species groups - this often requires expertise in marine ecology/taxonomy, which could then end up being costly
Combining with other sensors such as drones and AUVs to improve mapping	Data load and computational requirements may create bottlenecks or require large resources
Use of AI to improve classification and sensor development	

Drones and aerial platforms

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Method description

Flying and surface drones (Figure 3) as a technology for assessing benthic habitats has developed from an emerging to a well-established technology, largely within the past decade. With the ongoing rapid developments, drones are well on its way to create a new standard of shallow water benthic habitat mapping and facilitate efficient, precise, reproducible, and low-emission collection of data in the coastal zone (Joyce et al., 2023).

Today flying drones in various forms and sizes are available for mapping and monitoring benthic habitats and species in shallow aquatic environments (Kvile et al., 2024). Their applications include mapping of aquatic vegetation, such as seagrass (e.g. Duffy et al., 2018; Hamad et al., 2022; Román et al., 2021), macroalgae and kelp forests (Cavanaugh et al., 2021; Rossiter et al., 2020), coastal wetlands (Doughty and Cavanaugh, 2019), coral reefs (Casella et al., 2017; Levy et al., 2018; Muslim et al., 2019), and seafloor substrates. Additionally, they are used to map benthic fauna like mussel and oyster beds, as well as seabirds (Edney et al., 2023) and marine mammals (Álvarez-González et al., 2023). Drones have also been used to detect anthropogenic pollutants, such as plastic debris (Torsvik et al., 2020) and oil spills (Adade et al., 2021).

Over the past few years, significant advancements in technical capabilities, including flying abilities and payload capacities of drones, along with sensor, software and algorithm development, has paved the way for a rapid development of their applications in research, mapping, and monitoring. Flying drones are scientifically often referred to as Unoccupied, Uncrewed, or Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). We advocate for the use of the gender-neutral terms “Unoccupied” or “Uncrewed” Aerial Vehicles (UAV) within science and management context (as suggested by Joyce et al. 2021).

In addition to UAV’s, surface drones and underwater drones are also important technologies for marine research and surveys purposes. Surface drones are often referred to as Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USV, Figure 3), and underwater drones as Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs),

s, or Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs). USVs have in multiple ways comparable capabilities to flying drones and can be equipped with a range of optical and acoustic sensors for data collection in water bodies and of seafloor bathymetry, species and habitats roving high-accuracy spatial data (<3 cm, georeferenced, Mogstad et al., 2019; Specht et al., 2020). ROVs are described in later sections.

Figure 3. A flying drone (Unoccupied Aerial Vehicle, UAV) and a surface drone (Unoccupied Surface Vehicle, USV) mapping benthic habitats and submerged aquatic vegetation. In the foreground a marine biologist collecting georeferenced ground truth data for training of AI/ML classification algorithms in the Oslofjord, Norway. Image by SeaBee/NIVA (June 2021).

Mapping and monitoring using UAVs are primarily based on optical sensors that operate in the visible and infrared part of the electromagnetic spectrum. This enables the identification of species and habitats through their “optical fingerprint”, which refers to the unique spectral signature of the object of interest. The most basic optical sensors mounted on drones are often RGB cameras, followed by multispectral (MSI) and hyperspectral (HSI) imaging systems. Typically, these sensors offer pixel resolutions (ground sampling distance, GSD) of 1 to 10 cm at flying altitudes from 40 to 120 m, depending on sensor resolution. RGB sensors, being cheaper and easier to apply, do not provide radiometrically accurate data, making them less efficient for quantitative habitat mapping compared to MSI and HSI. The latter allow for more complex recognition algorithms but requires more advanced data processing and are more expensive. Laser-induced sensors have shown promising results for shallow water bathymetry mapping, while thermal sensors (infrared cameras) are useful for detection of warm-blooded animals and measuring environmental temperature gradients. However, the integration of laser and thermal sensors with flying drones is still at an early stage. The advantages and limitations of different drones and sensors applicable for benthic applications are summarised in Table 3.

Optical techniques enable the precise identification of objects, vegetation elements, and animal species across various habitats by comparing the spectral data to established databases or by training of machine learning (ML) algorithms and recognition networks (Liu et al., 2022). The OBAMA-NEXT deliverable 4.1 details technical artificial intelligence solutions with user needs (Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2024). This approach thus

facilitates the differentiation between relevant habitats and species, as well as the accurate classification and mapping of their extent and distribution. Sophisticated AI/ML approaches also allow for the estimation of uncertainty in both quantitative (coverage and distribution) and qualitative (probability of prediction) parameters.

Table 5. Advantages and limitations of different drones and optical sensors applicable for shallow water and coastal habitat mapping. Modified from Kvile et al. (2024).

Equipment type	Application	Advantages	Limitations
Drones for aerial survey			
Rotor drones (e.g., DJI MATRICE 300 RTK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adjustable flight speed/stand-still Higher spatial resolution Large payload capacity Low and high altitude Vertical take-off and landing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited areal coverage
Fixed wing drones (e.g., SenseFly eBee)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large scale mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient Larger aerial coverage Long distance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smaller payload capacity Large landing zone (unless equipped with VTOL) Susceptible to wind direction Fixed flight speed Risk of smearing at low altitudes
Sensors (cameras) attached to the drone			
Red, green and blue (RGB) sensors (e.g., SONY RX1RM2 42MP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annotation and study site overview Simple habitat classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> True colours (as seen) High pixel resolution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low spectral resolution and low sensitivity for species and habitat recognition Not radiometrically correct (overlap between colours)
Multispectral imagery (MSI) sensors (e.g., MicaSense Altum 5band)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advanced/ detailed habitat classification Pixel-wise thematic mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several images at specific wavelengths Radiometrically correct colour sensing Enable comparison with spectral reflectance libraries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less suitable for annotation because of false colour images Lower pixel resolution Requires increase computer processing
Hyperspectral imagery (HSI) sensors (e.g., Specim AFX10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Species detection, detailed habitat classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High spectral resolution Can reconstruct true colour images Potential for physiological and ecological status assessment of marine vegetation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low light sensitivity and pixel resolution Requires complex data handling Creates large amounts of “non-essential” data Heavy weight and expensive

Applications

Aerial drones provide a novel and complementary technology by enabling cost-effective, high-resolution (centimetre-scale), and on-demand data collection. In addition, advantages include the ability to operate below cloud cover and the property to facilitate systematic and repetitive data acquisition (Joyce et al., 2023). An example from Sweden (Huber et al., 2022) demonstrates the complementary use of drone imagery with satellite images, where higher resolution imagery from flying drone images are used in assessing the accuracy of satellite classification. Other studies have shown the potential for upscaling detailed drone-collected data to satellite resolutions (Lu et al., 2024; Martínez Prentice et al., 2024).

Traditional methods generally fall short for efficient mapping of the often very heterogeneous distribution of species and habitats in shallow water coastal zones. While satellite remote sensing offers large spatial coverage, they are compared to drones at a lower spatial resolution, often at tens to hundreds of meter scales (Cavanaugh et al., 2021; Lønborg et al., 2022, Table 2) and is more limited by cloud cover and overflight flexibility. Sensor-equipped airplanes can overcome some of these challenges (Valle et al., 2015), however, their limited availability, the need for highly skilled operators (pilots) and high costs make them less feasible. Larger research vessels are limited to water depths greater than approximately 10 meters and have high operational costs. In contrast, smaller crewed boats cover limited areas and require significant time investment. SCUBA diving covers even smaller areas and is expensive (Féral and Norro, 2023). Also, the latter two methods often suffer from not being spatially explicit (Murphy and Jenkins, 2010).

Compared to traditional methods, drones offer a bird's-eye perspective on coastal ecosystems, capturing data at a resolution approximately 100 times higher than satellites. Their flexibility in timing and frequency permits studies at specific tide stages or before and after events (Casella et al., 2017), even in hazardous environments. While there are still no standardised protocols for estimating biodiversity or ecological status from drone data, it is indeed possible to identify and map the extent and distribution of habitats known for hosting rich (or poor) biodiversity and to derive relevant information needed to estimate the carbon uptake and storage capacity of a region, as well as assess environmental status. Limitations for drone data collection include winds (recommended <10 m/s), water transparency (that can be challenged in coastal and urban areas due to algae blooms, dissolved organic matter and suspended particles), sun glints (Muslim et al., 2019), flight restriction zone (national authorities), and adequate referencing if several datasets are compared and overlays (requiring high accuracy GNSS, <1-3 cm).

Figure 4 illustrates the mapping and habitat classification of a kelp forest ecosystem, known for its high biodiversity, within the complex archipelago of Helgelandskysten, Norway. Using a fixed-wing drone equipped with RGB and MSI sensors, single images were combined to create a georeferenced orthomosaic with a GSD of 3 cm per pixel, using the method described in Kvile et al. (2024). Ground truth observations of kelp and macroalgae species, sandy sediments, and rocks were used to train a machine learning algorithm for predicting habitat classes in the orthomosaic. An evaluation of the classification's predictive accuracy, through a confusion matrix, revealed accuracies for classifying kelp, macroalgae, sand and rock ranging between 70 and 98% (data not shown).

Figure 4. Mapping of macroalgae forests is an emerging application for drone-based mapping of benthic habitats. Kelp forests constitute a particular complex case, as kelp grows to depths of more than 30 meters on often steep rocky substrates and at exposed locations. Here an example of an RGB image (left) and habitat classification map (right) derived from drone-collected MSI data and AI/ML-based data analysis. The coloured codes refer to different habitat classes, such as *Laminaria hyperborea* (LAMHY), *Fucus serratus* (FUCSE). Modified from Gundersen et al. (in prep.). Both the drone image and the resulting habitat map have a pixel resolution of approximately 2 cm.

In conclusion, although drone imagery cannot entirely replace traditional coastal mapping methods, it serves as a cost-effective complement. Together with emerging technologies such as uncrewed surface and underwater vehicles, drones offer valuable prospects for digitised and replicable ecosystem monitoring and research. Given these advancements, drone-based methodologies could be endorsed as preferred procedures for ecosystem mapping and monitoring (Kandrot et al., 2022), aligning with protocols and policies such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and the Natura 2000 (founded on the Habitats Directive and the Birds Directive). Such embedding would strengthen future coastal management and regulations by providing decision-makers with precise, comprehensive, and current data. Furthermore, drone products can provide valuable ground truth data for calibrating and validation of coarser resolution data such as obtained using Sentinel-2 satellites. This potential will be investigated during a coherent mapping study under the OBAMA-NEXT project during the summer of 2024.

Technology readiness level

The use of drones, in combination with AI for benthic observations, such as the mapping of coastal habitats has likely reached a TRL of 6 to 7. Drones have proven to be particularly effective in mapping shallow water sandy bottoms, seagrass, and other submerged aquatic vegetation (Duffy et al., 2018; Hamad et al., 2022; Román et al., 2021), as well as littoral and surface/floating macroalgae (Cavanaugh et al., 2021; Rossiter et al., 2020). These habitat classes can be distinct from their spectral signatures and classified accordingly using AI data analysis. Implementing this technology to regular monitoring programs could advance its readiness to TRL 8 and 9.

However, there are also some more advanced aspects of benthic monitoring and mapping using drones, such as distinguishing macroalgae at the species level (Svane et al., 2022), detecting vegetation at depths beyond a few meters, including forest-forming, non-floating kelp species, and assessing quality status of habitats. These areas of research are currently regarded as TRL 4 or TRL 5, as there are few publications on this development level yet (but see seabee.no).

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using drones are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 6 and 7. Ecosystem health status assessments based on drone data is a current research topic.

Table 6. EBVs that can be addressed by drone and aerial platform-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Species traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phenology - Reproduction
Ecosystem functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary productivity - Ecosystem phenology - Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 7. EOVs that can be addressed by drone and aerial platform-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat extent - Essential fish habitat extent
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent of seagrass meadows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global and regional seagrass distribution - Contributions to blue" carbon storage - Essential fish habitat extent - Seagrass habitat fragmentation

Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent - Total habitable substrate (less sand/silt substrates, structural complexity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of coral cover and areal extent - Coral reef habitat classifications, mapped layers
Mangrove cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mangrove fringe width and area - Mangrove tree species composition and zonation 	
Marine turtle, bird and mammal abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species presence/absence - Count data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Density - Hotspots - Habitat maps

Technology SWOT: Drones and aerial platforms

Strengths	Weaknesses
Produces full cover georeferenced map products at a very high spatial resolution (cm level)	Limited areal coverage compared to e.g., spatial distribution models (SDMs) unless upscaled using satellite images
Cost-effective compared to traditional survey methods	Some weather restrictions on drone missions, such as wind speed < 10 m/s
Create time-series / repeatability / reproducible	Water depth is a limitation. Requires clear water for benthic mapping (low concentrations of microalgae, organic matter and particles). Not relevant for seabird mapping.
High degree of automation is possible, both in the data collection and analysis process	Requires high degree of technical skills to operate drones and analysing the data
Access of remote or difficult-to-access areas	Requires access to ample computational power for data analysis, especially with large datasets (>1 km ²)
Less disturbing to wildlife than traditional manual survey methods with presence of humans	
An efficient way to collect data for ground truth annotation and calibration of satellite imagery	
Opportunities	Threats
Cost-effective, standardised, repeated monitoring	Some privacy and ethical concerns regarding data collection using drones
Multipurpose usage of collected and shared drone images	Scepticism towards flying drones due to its military applications
Availability of open-source software for data acquisition and processing (e.g., WebODM)	Challenges in storage and computational resources due to a vast amount of data and intensive analyses
Drone swarm technology that can offer the possibility to use multiple drones to cover bigger areas or do the job faster	

Remotely Operated Vehicles and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles

Mihailo Azhar (AU), Anna Rubio (AZTI) and Irene Ruiz (AZTI)

Method description

Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) are underwater robotics platforms that can be equipped with a range of sensors for capturing high-resolution data for benthic mapping and monitoring. The two platforms largely differ by their operation; ROVs are tethered to a control system surface-side, whereas AUVs are untethered and can navigate autonomously.

In ROVs, the tether can provide both power to the vehicle, and real-time video and data streams. The real-time data streams enable a surface-side operator to finely control and supervise the vehicle during operation. The data streams can also be processed by ship-based computers enabling immediate analysis and decision-making. This responsive set-up enables ROVs to be used in regions with high-bathymetric relief, steep changes in bathymetric slope and around complex structures where fine manipulation is often required (Armstrong et al., 2019). However, additional acoustic positioning sensors such as Doppler velocity logs (DVL), ultra-short baseline (USBL) sensors or underwater GPS are often required to achieve dead reckoning and repeatable positioning information with ROVs. Furthermore, power delivery over the tether enables ROVs to operate with less time constraints. The tether, however, also limits the range of operation and needs to be properly managed to avoid entanglement. ROVs are typically classified into several classes based on capabilities, size, and operational use, with the smaller (< 100 kg) observation class ROVs (OCROV) typically used for benthic video surveys (Christ and Wernli, 2011).

Conversely, AUVs are untethered in their operation and navigate autonomously. They rely on numerous on-board positional sensors, like accelerometers, gyroscopes and Doppler velocity logs (DVL) to obtain heading and orientation during operation. In some applications, the AUVs are also able to surface periodically to obtain satellite-positioning GPS. The untethered operation allows AUVs to cover larger areas operating at durations from hours to several days and at depths up to 6000 m (Huvenne et al., 2018; Salavasidis et al., 2018). The endurance of an AUV is largely dependent on the size of the vehicle, so that larger batteries can be used, and the number of on-board sensors which consume power. Mission planning is important for AUVs as there is limited communication with the vehicle once deployed. Mission plans are uploaded to the AUV before deployment and carried out autonomously with little to no operator updates during the mission. Any tasks carried out during deployment are pre-programmed into the on-board sensors or tools. Developments in computer vision and machine learning will in time enable AUVs to carry out more complex navigational tasks including adaptive planning and have already demonstrated capabilities in target seeking (Yamahara et al.,

2019). Like ROVs, AUVs come in a range of sizes depending on endurance (depth and duration of operation) and sensor payload with small AUVs capable of deployment from shore (Jones et al., 2019; Roper et al., 2017).

Gliders are a specific type of AUVs whose main characteristic is the absence of propellers, and the use of variable buoyancy and wings to glide forward while descending or ascending through the water (this characteristic makes them more silent and have longer autonomy). Most glider solutions, allow today for exploration of the water column up to a depth of 1000 meters. Initially equipped with CTD and standard biogeochemical and acoustic sensors, the possibilities of more sophisticated sensors are increasing with time. Gliders enable the monitoring of pelagic habitats at unprecedented small temporal and spatial scales, however, their use for benthic and demersal studies is more limited since they are designed to work following a saw tooth path and do not remain close to the bottom for longer periods. The increasing availability of acoustic sensors in gliders payloads and new navigation modes, which allow some glider types to remain within a given depth of the seafloor, can offer interesting perspectives for benthic applications.

Applications

The primary sensor attached to both platforms are optical, predominantly RGB cameras in a single or multi-view arrangement. ROV deployments typically include flood light illumination while AUV deployments use HDR cameras and strobe lights due to battery constraints (Williams et al., 2016).

Similar to UAV platforms, high resolution images captured by these ROVs and AUVs cameras systems are turned into orthomosaics for visual analysis (Ferrari et al., 2016; Mejía-Mercado and Baco, 2023) and automated with ML algorithms (Martin-Abadal et al., 2018). Video data can also be used for species detection (Armstrong et al., 2019), in visual surveys and through structure-from-motion (SfM) to create 3D reconstruction of benthic habitats which can be further improved with sensor fusion through simultaneous localisation and mapping (SLAM) algorithms (Williams et al., 2016). Laser-based imaging sensors have been used on both platforms and laser-based 3D reconstruction systems can capture 3D geometric data of benthic habitats (Bodenmann et al., 2017; Massot-Campos and Oliver-Codina, 2015).

Acoustic sensors such as multi-beam echo sounders (MBES), side-scan sonars (SSS) and synthetic aperture sonars are also commonly deployed on both platforms to collect swath bathymetry and other geomorphometric data (Wynn et al., 2014). These acoustic sensors are predominantly used on AUV platforms as the decoupling between sea surface conditions and vehicle (due to the lack of tether) is important for a steady acquisition altitude (Jones et al., 2019). ROVs have additional capabilities with attachable robotic manipulators, “grippers”, that can be used to acquire samples. The choice of manipulator and manipulator sequence are dependent on the target species (Mazzeo et al., 2022) and on the expertise of the manipulator.

Auxiliary sensors and sampling tools can be fitted to both platforms to collect additional environmental data during primary acquisition. Fluorometer sensors can be attached for measuring chlorophyll *a*, coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) and turbidity, while conductivity-temperature-depth sensors create water column profiles. More recently, custom made water sampling tools for eDNA have been fitted to AUVs for wide range temporal and spatial sampling (Yamahara et al., 2019).

Technology readiness level

In benthic habitat mapping, both AUVs and ROVs have been implemented in the Australian state benthic monitoring programs (Przeslawski and Foster, 2020) placing them at TRL 8-9. It should be noted that AUVs and ROVs are used as platforms for other instrumentations and therefore their readiness is also limited by the TRL of those instruments. As an example, extracting samples with ROVs and an actuator are limited by robotic arm development and are not as mature as imaging sensors.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using ROV and AUV methods are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 8 and 9. Relevant benthic EOVs include fish abundance and distribution, macroalgal canopy cover and composition, seagrass cover and composition, hard coral cover, and composition as well as mangrove cover and composition.

Table 8. EBVs that can be addressed by mooring, cable observatory and lander-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Species traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Movement - Reproduction
Community composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community abundance - Taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity - Trait diversity
Ecosystem functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem phenology - Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 9. EOVs that can be addressed by ROV and AUV-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy species diversity - Plant condition (qualitative: signs of necrosis and potential drivers, fouling and grazing) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat extent - Essential fish habitat extent

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent 	
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shoot density/cover - Seagrass diversity (species) - Areal extent of seagrass meadows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global and regional seagrass distribution - Essential fish habitat extent - Seagrass habitat fragmentation
Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent - Coral diversity (species, genera and functional type; and alpha, beta or gamma) - Coral condition (diseases, bleaching, mortality (partial and full), predated, silted, other conditions/syndromes) - Total habitable substrate (less sand/silt substrates, structural complexity) - Coral size classes (recruits/small corals, size class distribution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of coral cover and areal extent - Inventories of coral diversity - Coral condition - Coral recruitment and size class distributions - Coral reef habitat classifications, mapped layers
Fish abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numbers or biomass of fish by size/age/stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish habitat

Technology SWOT: Remotely Operated Vehicle and Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

Strengths	Weaknesses
Flexible platforms for numerous sensors Cost effective compared to traditional survey High-resolution sampling possible Access to difficult-to-access areas Numerous models cost/size for different needs	Further processing of gathered data usually required ROV: Limited coverage compared to AUV. Underwater positioning requires additional sensors Sediment disturbance by thrusters Requires technical skill to operate Require constant supervision and control from trained operators, which increases costs.
AUV: Large km scale coverage possible Autonomous targetable navigation and sampling possible ROV: Precision control: Operators can manipulate ROVs with precision allowing for detailed exploration and can adapt the mission ensuring accurate data collection Off-the-shelf components are plentiful	AUV: Battery capacity limitations Autonomous navigation in complex environments is difficult Sensors are often custom made More sophisticated mission planning required
Opportunities	Threats

<p>Long term continuous monitoring on the horizon. Integration with AI and ML could streamline data analysis and decision-making processes for both AUVs and ROVs</p> <p>Collaborative efforts between AUVs and ROVs for improved coverage and mapping accuracy</p> <p>AUV:</p> <p>More sophisticated autonomous navigation. Swarm monitoring with multiple AUVs More off-the-shelf sensors for AUVs</p> <p>Integration of AUVs with other RS data such as satellites could provide more comprehensive covering broader spatial scale than what could be covered by AUVs</p>	<p>ROV:</p> <p>Rapid advancements in AUVs, which are untethered and more autonomous and efficient compared to ROVs could lead to ROVs being less popular or even obsolete</p> <p>AUV:</p> <p>Collision risks Technological limitation due to battery life</p>
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Moorings, cabled observatories, and landers

Anna Rubio (AZTI) and Irene Ruiz (AZTI)

Method description

Benthic oceanographic moorings are scientific platforms composed by a set of sensors connected to a wire and anchored on the sea floor, designed to study the conditions and processes occurring near the seabed. Moorings have been a common method for long-term ocean data sampling, and long-time used for hydrography, hydrodynamic and sedimentology studies. With the arrival of new compact sensors, the installation of cameras or acoustic instruments has allowed their use for other purposes, like the study of demersal fish. Cabled observatories, also anchored to the sea floor much closer to the coast, have the benefit of high-power cable connections that can support a variety of sensors such as cameras and microphones that can take high-definition audio and video, and standard sensors that measure biogeochemical properties. These observatories enable real-time monitoring and continuous data collection of benthic environments and their associated processes. Landers, another type of seafloor platforms, are deployed from ships and lowered to the seafloor. They allow to observe and study benthic environments in greater detail than traditional methods like ROVs or manned submersibles. Landers can be equipped with a variety of sensors to measure parameters such as temperature, salinity, pressure, oxygen levels, and currents. They can also carry cameras and other imaging equipment to capture high-resolution images and video footage of the seafloor and benthic organisms. As cabled observatories, landers can remain stationary on the seafloor for extended periods, allowing for long-term monitoring and continuous data collection.

Applications

The benthic examples found in the literature include direct or potential applications to the monitoring of demersal fish and benthic fauna. Also, an example is found for the characterization and monitoring of substrate changes (Rock, Sand, Other potential application).

- Acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs) deployed via mooring enable the collection of echo intensity values and vertical velocity profiles, crucial for observing phenomena like zooplankton migration, with potential applications to benthic fauna. This technology, as demonstrated in the Lembeh Strait in the Central Indo-Pacific, provides valuable insights into diel vertical migration, as studied by Dwinovantyo et al. (2019), at depths of up to 20 m. Multi-frequency sonar systems can also be moored to enable automated data collection for acquiring information about zooplankton and fish species composition and abundance through acoustic backscatter data. These systems, like the standard AZFP, can be moored at depths up to 300 m, or even 600 m with modified transducers, as demonstrated by Lemon et al., (2012).
- Nowadays, NEPTUNE Canada observatory located off the west coast of Vancouver Island, Canada and OBSEA located off the coast of Tarragona, Spain, in the western Mediterranean Sea offer valuable insights into benthic ecosystems and their role in the broader marine environment. One specific study conducted using NEPTUNE Canada focused on monitoring the biodiversity of deep-sea benthic fauna using high-definition video cameras to survey faunal populations along the seafloor (Juniper et al., 2013). Researchers have also used OBSEA to study the biodiversity of benthic ecosystems in the Mediterranean by integrating a benthic crawler to extend its monitoring radius and collect more ecologically representative data (Falahzadeh et al., 2023). As technology continues to evolve, cabled observatories are expected to play an increasingly important role in benthic research and monitoring efforts.
- The Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6), utilizing electromagnetic wave sensing, is deployed via mooring and efficiently records particle numbers and images of large targets every 40 seconds, showcasing its potential application to benthic fauna studies. This technology, exemplified in Svalbard in the Arctic, provides valuable insights into particle size spectra and plankton, as demonstrated by Picheral et al. (2022), at depths of up to 50 m. UVP6 can be also integrated into glider-based monitoring systems to enhance the ability to study benthic ecosystems efficiently and comprehensively (Picheral et al., 2022)
- Acoustic echo sounders installed on gliders, such as the IMAGENEX 385, enable automated data collection of pelagic habitats with a resolution as fine as 0.5 m, depending on the acoustic probe and configuration used. This technology allows for *in situ* optical (video) data collection in global regions. In this example an application in the Weddell Sea, at depths of up to 1000 m, is showcased (Guihen et al., 2014).
- Side-scan sonar technology, deployed via moorings, buoys or floats, offers potential applications in substrate characterization, particularly in rock, sand, and other substrates. This autonomous system enables automated data collection for bathymetry and positioning, with a typical autonomy of a few tens of days, as demonstrated by Zhou et al. (2014) in the Arctic and eastern Greenland at depths of up to 200 m.

Technology readiness level

TRL8-9 generally represents the advanced stage for these technologies. However, their application in benthic studies is less common as they were originally designed for the water column, with limited testing in benthic ecosystems. As these technologies undergo more rigorous testing and validation in these environments, their readiness for practical deployment and commercialization in benthic studies will increase.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using platforms such as moorings, cable observatories and landers are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 10 and 11.

Table 10. EBVs that can be addressed by mooring, cable observatory and lander-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	- Species abundance
Species traits	- Movement
Community composition	- Community abundance - Taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity
Ecosystem functioning	- Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	- Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 11. EOVs that can be addressed by mooring, cable observatory and lander-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent - Coral diversity (species, genera and functional type; and alpha, beta or gamma) - Coral condition (diseases, bleaching, mortality (partial and full), predated, silted, other conditions/syndromes) - Total habitable substrate (less sand/silt substrates, structural complexity) - Coral size classes (recruits/small corals, size class distribution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of coral cover and areal extent - Inventories of coral diversity - Coral condition - Coral recruitment and size class distributions - Coral reef habitat classifications, mapped layers

Fish abundance and distribution	- Numbers or biomass of fish by size/age/stage	- Fish abundance indices - Fish diversity indices
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Technology SWOT: Moorings, cabled observatories and landers

Strengths	Weaknesses
Moorings, cabled observatories and landers: long-term monitoring, stable platform flexible instrumentation.	Moorings, cabled observatories and landers: limited mobility, deployment and recovery challenges
Opportunities	Threats
Moorings, cabled observatories and landers: they can support multidisciplinary studies by integrating data from multiple sensors and instruments	Moorings, cabled observatories and landers: seabed disturbance

Flow cytometry and flow imaging microscopy

Louise Forsblom (Syke) and Mari Vanharanta (Syke)

Method description

Flow cytometry has mainly been applied to pelagic systems, but the method has also been applied within soil science (El Mujtar et al., 2022). This section only considers benthic applications and for an in depth overview of the pelagic applications please see the review of existing and emerging technologies for pelagic observations, deliverable 2.1, (Palazot et al. 2024). Much less work has been published on the method in connection to benthic microorganisms and a Web-of-Science search with the key words benthic and flow cytometry yielded 86 articles (March 2024) and benthic and flow image microscopy yielded only eight.

Flow cytometry (FCM) is a single-cell approach that has been widely used in oceanography since the 1980s (Olson et al., 1989; Trask et al., 1982; Yentsch et al., 1983). In the field of marine microbial ecology, it is utilised to study spatial and temporal distribution, composition and functions of eukaryotic and prokaryotic microbial organisms and virus like particles. The method is based on detection of single cell properties as the sample particles line up individually in a narrow laminar flow and pass through a laser beam. As the particle intersects with the laser beam, light scattering will be detected and used as a proxy of particle size and fluorescence

properties of pigments or fluorescent dyes. Flow cytometers can be equipped with lasers of various wavelengths to target specific chromophores.

Photosynthetic organisms, i.e., prokaryotic and eukaryotic phytoplankton, can be detected by their red fluorescence from Chlorophyll pigments in an unprocessed water sample, but heterotrophic organisms require prior staining by, e.g., nucleic-acid stains to be separated from abiotic particles like mineral particles and detritus. Post-processing and characterization of microbial populations are done afterwards with two-dimensional cytograms in an instrument specific software.

Flow imaging microscopy (FIM) captures digital images of magnified particles within a fluid stream targeting larger particles (up to 5 mm) compared to FCM but does not capture the smallest size classes nor provide data on fluorescence properties. We could only identify five articles for FIM (FlowCam + benthic). There are, however, some examples where either FCM or FIM have been used for e.g. investigating biofilms in streams (Villeneuve et al., 2010), bacterial communities associated to sediments in the Mediterranean and Black Sea (Rubin-Blum et al., 2022), benthic *Microcystis* in freshwater (Zhou et al., 2012), as well as to study meiofaunal communities off the coast of Japan using FlowCam (Kitahashi et al., 2018). Investigating biofilms only required the scraping of the community from the surface it was attached to, but, e.g., extraction of bacteria and meiofauna required pre-processing of the sediment samples to remove the sediment particles prior to the analysis (Amalfitano and Puddu, 2009; Deng et al., 2019).

Applications

We found no direct applications of FCM or FIM for the monitoring of benthic habitats. But considering microorganisms in the sediment could be warranted in the future as microorganisms are the drivers of biogeochemical cycles, and are of major importance in carbon cycling in the sediments (Hicks et al., 2018), but for quantifying biodiversity, genetic approaches are necessary. FCM has been shown to enable efficient processing of the enumeration of prokaryotes in sediments (Lavergne et al., 2014).

Technology readiness level

Methods such as FCM are in operational use and have TRL 9 in pelagic environments, however, as the benthic cases highlighted in the section above are few they would receive approximately TRL 3-6.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using FCM and flow imaging microscopy methods are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 12 and 13. There is no EOv currently targeting microbes in the sediment, even though a microbe biomass and diversity pilot is mentioned on the GOOS webpage (<https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>).

Table 12. EBVs that can be addressed by FCM and FIM-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON

(<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	- Species abundance
Species traits	- Morphology
Community composition	- Community abundance - Trait diversity
Ecosystem functioning	- Primary productivity

Technology SWOT: Flow Cytometry and flow imaging microscopy

Strengths	Weaknesses
Already well-established protocols for pelagic sampling	Spatial extent quite limited and unlike pelagic flow cytometry, more difficult to automate due to the sediment pre-processing step
Opportunities	Threats
Increase the speed of sample processing	

Photogrammetry and drop videos

Jaakko Haapamäki (Syke), Ville Karvinen (Syke) and Dimitar Berov (IO-BAS/IBER-BAS)

Method description

Mapping or monitoring habitats using images or videos is called imaging. It can be used to map and monitor benthic fauna, seagrass, macroalgae, corals and other aquatic vegetation and substrate. Images and videos can be produced by an automated vessel with a submerged camera system, by towing a camera from a manned vessel, by a diver using a camera or by attaching the equipment to a platform (Oh et al., 2020; Rende et al., 2020). The images and videos can be analysed either on site or later. Analysis can be done by an expert or by automatically classifying images by for example spectral, colour or shape using object-based image analysis (OBIA). Object based image analysis enables better accuracy when using automation in analysing images. Imaging is well suited for mapping and monitoring habitats when high-resolution data are needed and for ground truthing. Resolution is usually high (5-10 cm) (Rende et al., 2020).

Photography and videography have long been an integral part of scuba diver, submersible, ROV and AUV underwater surveys of biodiversity, ecosystems state and functioning both in shallow coastal ecosystems and in deep-sea research (Ballesteros, 1992; Carleton and Done, 1995; Klöser et al., 1996; Lundälv et al., 1986; Norris et al., 1997; Whorff and Griffing, 1992). The advent of digital photography in the early 2000s made imaging techniques both more efficient in terms of amounts of data collection and more accessible and easy to use (Preskitt et al., 2004; Roelfsema and Phinn, 2009; Vroom and Page, 2006; Vroom and Timmers, 2009). Digital photos and videos data can easily be stored, copied, transferred, and analysed. Digital images can also easily be integrated with other *in situ* data – georeferencing and *in situ* measurements of the marine environment. The wide availability of good quality professional digital cameras and later ‘action’ cameras gave coastal ecosystem researchers powerful tools for efficient data collection at a relatively low price (Raoult et al., 2016).

The continuous development of new and accessible digital still cameras and video cameras has led to an ever-increasing quality of the images that can be collected during underwater surveys. New cameras with higher pixel resolution and better light sensitivity allow researchers to collect high quality image data even in areas with lower water transparency and higher turbidity. New generations of ‘action’ cameras with increased video frame resolution (4K, 8K) continuously bring the price of image acquisition down while improving the quality and ease of collection for video- and still-image data in underwater surveys. The quality and ease of collection for *in situ* data are further improved with the availability of commercial still image and video cameras dedicated to underwater work, as well as image quality correction algorithms both integrated in the camera’s software (e.g. Paralenz, Go Pro, Nikon W300, Olympus TG6), or as a still image post-processing software procedure like Sea-thru (Akkaynak and Treibitz, 2019). Recent improvements of ease of data collection in shallow-water scuba surveys include the development of commercially available cameras that have integrated depth and temperature sensors (Paralenz).

Advances in affordable methods for underwater geolocation of scuba divers also greatly improved the efficiency of video- and photo-surveys of benthic ecosystems. These include the UWIS underwater navigation, communications and surveillance system (UWIS Inc., Finland), which can be used by divers, as well as the diver propulsion system-based (DPS) ENC3-PRO underwater navigation system (Marine Tech SA), and the DRIVE SINAPSI system (SUEX, Italy). The use of such systems greatly improves the precision of georeferencing of photo sampling during underwater scuba surveys, building on the widely used methods for georeferencing using surface-mounted GPS buoys and later positional and image data synchronization (Berov et al., 2018; Roelfsema and Phinn, 2009).

Photogrammetry is a method for making accurate measurements from photographs using the principles of optics (Campbell and Wynne, 2011). This can be achieved by, for example, calculating the dimensions of a habitat from images by using overlap. This enables construction of 3D images that, in turn, can improve the accuracy in automated calculations, enable calculation of biomass and improve the classification of images. Structure from motion photogrammetry is an emerging image analysis technology that allows the creation of high-resolution 3D models of objects in the natural environment (Burns and Delparte, 2017). The technology

reconstructs a 3D model from overlapping single-lens camera photos, thus eliminating the need for expensive and complex stereo cameras. A commonly used software for 3D photogrammetry is the Agisoft Metashape, which is widely used in benthic ecology studies in tropical coral reef studies, temperate seas benthic communities' studies, as well as underwater archaeology. Besides 3D model reconstruction and structural complexity analyses, the methodology is extremely useful for non-destructive volume and biomass estimations of sessile species, allowing researchers to track the productivity and growth rates of organisms in benthic ecosystems without collecting specimens (Lange and Perry, 2020; Marlow et al., 2024).

Applications

Imaging is a method that produces high-resolution data from underwater environments but with limited scale. It can be used for ground truthing for remote sensing technologies (Rende et al., 2020) but monitoring can be less accurate due to limited range of the video and difficulties repeating the same spatial coverage in different instances. Data produced by imaging can be very useful for determining biodiversity because of its accuracy.

A significant challenge in the use of photos and videos for benthic ecosystems research is the ease and efficiency of image analysis and extraction of relevant biodiversity, size estimations and community structure data from the collected images. Traditionally, images were analysed by experienced observers that manually identified visible macro-organisms, made frequency counts and measured sizes based on size references in planar images of the benthos (Ballesteros, 1992; Whorff and Griffing, 1992). A more efficient approach to quantify identifiable organisms is to estimate the frequency of their occurrence based on the classical point intercept method (Pielou, 1974). The currently widely adopted approach for image analysis employs manual annotation with software packages such as the Coral Point Count extension (Bryant et al., 2017; Roelfsema et al., 2013; Roelfsema and Phinn, 2009; Ryan, 2004), photoQuad (Langenkämper et al., 2017; Trygonis and Sini, 2012; Tsirintanis et al., 2018), or BIIGLE (Langenkämper et al., 2017). These software packages aid the analysis process through image analysis tools, creation of lists of typical species to be identified, automated point distribution for detection of these species, and generation of results in data sheets that can be linked with databases, thus greatly improving the efficiency of the 'manual' image annotation.

The recent development of machine learning algorithms for automated image recognition made its way in benthic image data analysis with semi-automated and automated algorithms used in deep-sea research (Beuchel et al., 2010; Purser et al., 2009), fish stock assessments (Richards et al., 2019), and tropical coral reef surveys (Beijbom et al., 2012; Marcos et al., 2005; Shihavuddin et al., 2013; Stokes and Deane, 2009). An emerging methodology for automated image analysis that also finds its way in temperate seas coastal benthic research is the CoralNET Deep Learning algorithm that is integrated with the widely used CPCe annotation procedure (Chen et al., 2021). The CoralNET methodology allows users to train custom algorithms for specific geographic areas by uploading human-annotated imagery (CPCe format), thus making use of the large datasets available in various research institutions. CoralNET offers a free online service where users can upload their

imagery and training data, make use of other training datasets and images (web browser interface). A CoralNet API solution is also available when users need to analyse large datasets (up to 100k+ images). CoralNET currently contains over 3.10^6 images with over 127.10^6 'manual' and automated annotations of benthic organisms. Additionally, considering spectral properties of species functional groups for corals, also has potential to improve species identification and annotation from images (Bollati et al., 2021; Zawada and Mazel, 2014).

A recent technological development in underwater benthic photography surveys is the construction of diver operated systems that combine photography and 3D photogrammetry, with hyperspectral imaging, acoustic depth sounding sonar and array of sensors measuring parameters such as dissolved oxygen, pH, PAR light. These systems could be mounted on a diver propulsion system (e.g. the Catlin Surveys SVII system) or have a neutral buoyancy and be moved underwater by the diver team (e.g. the HyperDiver system, Chennu et al. (2017)). A simplified and easy to use approach, during diver surveys, is the integration of multi-parameter probes measuring physico-chemical and biological parameters of the marine environment with camera and video surveys with subsequent timestamp data integration and georeferencing (Berov et al., 2018).

The gathering of large amounts of data from different instruments and sources during UW surveys, and their later integration with AUV and ROV underwater data, satellite, and drone multispectral data, require the development of streamlined data processing procedures that allows the integration and analysis of these data streams. Examples of such methodologies include the underwater photogrammetric pipeline for coral reef monitoring and change detection of Nocerino et al., (2020), the machine-learning based algorithm for benthic mapping with photomosaics and 3D model construction (Yuval et al., 2021), and the machine- and deep-learning based methodology of McKenzie et al., (2022) for seagrass beds mapping by integration of *in situ* survey data, with remote sensing data (drop cameras, sonars, airborne AUV and aircraft surveys, satellite observations data).

Technology readiness level

Imaging is widely used in mapping and monitoring, and the technological readiness level for the method is high. Automation in habitat classification is a more recent field but has seen some advances in recent years (Royer et al., 2018). TRL for imaging is estimated to be at level 9, but some aspects of it like image analysis and automation could still see some improvements having TRL 8.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using photogrammetry and drop video methods are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 14 and 15.

Table 13. EBVs that can be addressed by photogrammetry and drop-video-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Species traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Morphology - Phenology - Reproduction
Community composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community abundance - Taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity - Trait diversity
Ecosystem functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem phenology - Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 14. EOVs that can be addressed by photogrammetry and drop-video-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy species diversity - Canopy height - Stem density (kelps) - Plant condition (qualitative: signs of necrosis and potential drivers, fouling and grazing) - Plant size classes (including recruits) - Photosynthetic efficiency - Photosynthetic biomass - Areal extent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat extent - Canopy health indices - Global geographical distribution - Primary production - Essential fish habitat extent
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shoot density/cover - Canopy height - Seagrass diversity (species) - Areal extent of seagrass meadows - Photosynthetic efficiency (measured with PAM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary and secondary production - Global and regional seagrass distribution - Contributions to blue" carbon storage - Essential fish habitat extent

Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent - Coral diversity (species, genera and functional type; and alpha, beta or gamma) - Coral condition (diseases, bleaching, mortality (partial and full), predated, silted, other conditions/syndromes) - Total habitable substrate (less sand/silt substrates, structural complexity) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coral size classes (recruits/small corals, size class distribution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seagrass habitat fragmentation - Maps of coral cover and areal extent - Inventories of coral diversity - Coral condition - Coral recruitment and size class distributions - Coral reef habitat classifications, mapped layers - Coral reef system health (with key fish, urchins, macroalgae EOVs) - Convention indicators – Aichi Target 10, SDG 14.2/5, IPBES
Mangrove cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mangrove fringe width and area - Mangrove tree species composition and zonation - Tree, algae, and phytoplankton primary production - Canopy height and trunk girth - Trunk and seedling density by species - Soil profile, carbon/nutrient content, and 14C age - Sediment and water column respiration - Intertidal fish and invertebrate densities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Above- and below-ground biomass - Ecosystem gross and net primary production - Carbon sequestration rate - Fish and invertebrate productivity
Fish abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number, biomass or abundance index of fish of different taxa per unit volume or area of water in a specific region, stock or population, and measured by a standard or known protocol - Numbers or biomass of fish by size/age/stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish abundance indices - Fish diversity indices - Size-based indicators of fish assemblages, including mean fish size, size spectra, and large fish indicators - Food web indicators, including proportion of predatory fish

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish production - Fish habitat
Marine turtle, bird and mammal abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species presence/absence - Age - Sex - Count data - Repeated individual presence (tracking/resights) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Density - Hotspots - Home range - Utilization distribution (relative occupation of home range) - Movement patterns - Migration pathways - Habitat maps - Population status (increasing, decreasing stable)

Technology SWOT: imaging

Strengths	Weaknesses
High resolution	Limited by water attributes
Suitable for automation	Geolocation difficulties
Non destructive	Limited spatial scale unless attached to platform
Efficient and rapid data collection	High price of equipment and software
	Need for highly trained field researchers – boat crews, scientific divers, RO operators
	Lack of sufficient taxonomical accuracy of species identification from images; No actual biota samples are collected
Opportunities	Threats
Future improvement of accuracy and speed of image/video analysis by improvement of machine learning image analysis algorithms	Data loss
Rapid technological development with continuous improvement of available instruments	Loss of access to computational facilities for automated analysis of images/videos
Permanent database of images and videos that can be re-analysed in the future	

Acoustics

Valentina Todorova (IO-BAS)

Method description

Acoustic technologies use sound to explore and monitor the aquatic environment. In active acoustic methods (AAM) an electrical pulse generated by a transmitter passes through a transducer and is converted in sound wave. The sound travels through the water column and is scattered from the seabed or other targets, the backscatter is received by either the same transducer or one or more receivers and converted back to electrical energy. The electrical signal is amplified and filtered to generate convenient signal levels and to eliminate out-of-band noise. This review focuses on four basic types of AAM, which have been most widely used for habitat mapping and fisheries studies (Anderson et al., 2007; Brown et al., 2011): 1) Single-beam, Acoustic Ground Discrimination Systems (SB-AGDS); 2) Side-scan sonar systems (SSS); 3) Multibeam echosounders (MBES); 4) High-frequency multibeam forward-looking sonar (MFLS).

SB-AGDS are vertical-incidence systems using a single-beam transducer and typically range in frequency between 30 and 200 kHz (Brown, 2007; Lurton, 2002). A number of systems (e.g. RoxAnn, QTC-View, EchoPlus) have been used for habitat studies, all of which record depth and some measure of the backscatter signal relating to the properties of the seafloor (Anderson et al., 2007; Brown, 2007, p. 200). The data from SB-AGDS are usually divided into acoustic classes using signal-based segmentation of the returning echograms. To produce continuous coverage data layers of the segmented acoustic classes from SB-AGDS, it is necessary to interpolate the acoustic data between survey lines, having the potential to miss discrete features in the non-surveyed areas.

SSS are conceptually two echosounders in the same housing, with transducers positioned to transmit to port and starboard rather than vertically. Because of the large vertical beam width, SSS echoes are presented as a raster image. SSS systems operate at relatively high frequencies (100-500 kHz), recording acoustic backscatter data from a swath of seafloor in order to produce a textural image pertaining to the surficial seabed characteristics. By designing acoustic surveys with parallel track lines and with line spacing based on the swath dimensions of the SSS, it is relatively easy to collect continuous coverage data from an area of interest. Using the mosaicked imagery, segmentation of the backscatter data has conventionally been done by expert interpretation, whereby the imagery is divided into regions of similar texture or backscatter strength “by eye”. The acoustic segments are then linked to geological attributes from ground-truthing samples (Blondel, 2010). More recently, automated methods of segmenting SSS backscatter data have been used by means of objective classification algorithms applied to the backscatter data (Brown and Collier, 2008; Ehrhold et al., 2006; Lucieer, 2008). Automated segmentation methods can be broadly divided into two types: 1) image-based segmentation – backscatter image is divided into regions of similar characteristics (e.g. surface features, backscatter

intensity, textural features etc.) and 2) signal-based segmentation – changes in the backscatter intensity are analysed to classify the data.

For fisheries studies, SSS frequency is commonly >1100 kHz, with a sampling swath of 50–70 m, and the resolution can be <10 cm. This is efficient for sampling large water areas up to 100 m sampling range. MBES transmits similarly to the SSS but receives on transducer arrays. The backscatter data, combined with the availability of co-registered bathymetry, give more information than is available with SSS alone (Le Bas and Huvenne, 2009). MBES backscatter mosaics have been segmented by “expert” interpretation (Kostylev et al., 2003) or various image-based segmentation methods: neural network techniques (Marsh and Brown, 2009), principal components analysis of multiple backscatter image-based attributes (Brown, 2007; Chris McGonigle et al., 2010; Christopher McGonigle et al., 2010; McGonigle et al., 2011, 2009; Preston, 2009), Bayesian decision rules (Simons and Snellen, 2009); textural analysis based on grey level co-occurrence matrices (Blondel and Sichi, 2009), and creation of synthetic colour images (Ierodiaconou et al., 2007; Rattray et al., 2009). Signal-based methods have also been used to extract quantitative parameters from the backscatter signal, link acoustic backscatter observations to seafloor properties and predict the substratum (Fonseca et al., 2009; Lamarche et al., 2011).

MFLS has become a tool for fish detection, tracking and counting (Artero et al., 2021). The MFLS generates high-resolution image sequences by transmitting multiple fan-shaped beams simultaneously. The lower frequency MFLS (<1 MHz) are typically used for fish detection and counting in a large area. MFLS with a frequency greater than 1 MHz is capable to produce high-resolution images similar to optical cameras, thus earning the term of acoustic camera. The resolution of a high-frequency acoustic camera can be <1 cm. An ideal demersal species for evaluating acoustic camera capabilities under low visibility is the goliath grouper *Epinephelus itajara* (Artero et al., 2021).

Acoustic systems have limitations near boundaries. Due to the conical shape of the acoustic beam, echoes from the sea floor or air–water interface, which are much larger than echoes from fish, severely contaminate echoes from the water column, thus fish within 1–2 m of the bottom are not well detected (Mann et al., 2008). This effect can be reduced by towing the transducer closer to the seabed, but at the cost of reducing the sampling volume.

The process of validating acoustic data in terms of sediment composition, morphological structure, and biota is commonly referred to as ground truthing. A vast variety of *in situ* tools, e.g. conspicuous species, particle size distributions, in-fauna information, etc., have been used in seafloor habitat mapping studies (Anderson et al., 2007; Van Rein et al., 2009). Visual methods for ground truthing allow broad seabed categories to be identified relating to the surficial substrate characteristics. (e.g. sediment ripples, bed forms). Underwater video and still photography are valuable, non-destructive methods for the assessment of all types of seabed attributes. The scale at which seabed attributes can be defined is ultimately determined by the maximum resolution of the acoustic system and the limits of the ground-truthing accuracy with respect to positioning (Kenny et al., 2003).

Passive acoustics methods (PAM) use hydrophones to convert the sounds produced by animals into a voltage that can be recorded and analysed (Mancusi et al., 2023; Mann et al., 2008). Passive acoustics have been used

to study the reproductive behaviour of benthopelagic fishes of the family Sciaenidae, the croakers and drums, who form chorusing groups, as well as for detection and counting of reef-associated demersal fish such as damselfishes (Pomacentridae), who produce stereotypical sounds (Mann et al., 2008). The recorded sounds can be played back and the sounds characteristic of particular species identified by an experienced listener. Sounds can also be identified by converting them into sound spectrograms, which display changes in their frequency and temporal characteristics with time. Fish sounds also lend themselves to automated sampling and analysis. Beyond animal sounds, PAM captures the whole ambient soundscape. As such, it can also be used to measure noise pollution. Acoustic telemetry utilises animal borne tags (transmitters) that transmit coded signals at a specific frequency and can be logged by a researcher directly with a hydrophone from a boat (active tracking) or by using arrays of stationary *in situ* receivers with hydrophones attached, recording the presence of an individual within a particular area (passive tracking) (Ellis et al., 2019; Reubens et al., 2021).

Applications

Active acoustic methods are extensively used in mapping seafloor geomorphology, geology and habitats (Brown et al., 2011), for example cold water corals (Lim et al., 2021), seaweeds (Lønborg et al., 2022) and seagrass (Barrell et al., 2015), *Modiolus modiolus* beds (Brittany et al., 2021), faunal assemblages in cold seeps (Sen et al., 2016), intertidal ecosystems (Capperucci et al., 2020).

Active acoustic techniques are used in fish monitoring to identify fish, estimate abundance, evaluate spatial and temporal distributions; and measure size distributions and fish population structure (Mann et al., 2008). In addition, these methods can also be used to characterise habitats and study behaviours such as migration, spawning, feeding, and schooling.

Passive acoustics uses the sounds made by demersal and benthopelagic fishes to understand their distribution and, because most sounds are produced in relation to courtship and spawning, to understand the dynamics of spawning (Lindseth and Lobel, 2018). The technology provides utilitarian information to delimit spawning areas for conservation and management purposes.

Technology readiness level

AAM (generic sonars) and PAM (hydrophones) have long history of broad implementation in benthic habitat mapping and fish monitoring with many commercial applications and systems available on the market. Some continuing challenges are associated with signal interpretation, since the backscatter is influenced by numerous factors: the targets' acoustic characteristics, variable ocean conditions, movements of targets, proper calibration of acoustic instruments, boundary and depth limitations, and sound pollution. Handling large volumes of acoustic data requires robust processing algorithms and effective visualization tools. Automated methods of segmenting backscatter data have been used by means of objective classification algorithms: image-based and signal-based (AAM). Nowadays, machine learning and, in particular, deep learning represents the state of the art for processing audio signals. Specifically, sound separation networks can be successfully used to automatically extract fish vocalizations in PAM recordings. Overall, the acoustic

technologies have likely reached TRL 7 to TRL 9. Acoustic instruments can be expensive, uneven access to technology and expertise limiting their widespread deployment in marine monitoring.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using acoustic methods are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 16 and 17.

Table 15. EBVs that can be addressed by acoustic-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON

(<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Species traits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Movement
Ecosystem functioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem disturbance
Ecosystem structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem distribution - Ecosystem Vertical Profile

Table 16. EOVs that can be addressed by acoustic-based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOv that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOv. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOv and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOv, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat extent - Essential fish habitat extent
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Areal extent of seagrass meadows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global and regional seagrass distribution
Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Live hard coral cover and areal extent - Total habitable substrate (less sand/silt substrates, structural complexity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maps of coral cover and areal extent
Fish abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number, biomass or abundance index of fish of different taxa per unit volume or area of water in a specific region, stock or population, and measured by a standard or known protocol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish abundance indices

	- Numbers or biomass of fish by size/age/stage	
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Technology SWOT: Acoustics

Strengths	Weaknesses
Seabed mapping: direct, continuous, fast, non-destructive; automated methods of segmenting backscatter data: image-based or signal-based.	Scale mismatch of acoustic data and ground truth data may hinder acoustic “image” interpretation. Acoustic characteristics do not correspond to unique physical characteristics of the seabed.
Fish surveys: efficient in turbid water, large sampling range or high resolution depending on transmission frequency.	Limitations near boundaries: acoustic “dead zone” 1-2 m above the seabed.
Opportunities	Threats
Developing algorithms to process large data sets and to automatically classify the habitats and species under study.	Acoustic instruments can be expensive, uneven access to technology and expertise limiting their widespread deployment in marine monitoring.

Environmental DNA

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Method description

Biodiversity surveys in benthic ecosystems have traditionally relied on manual sorting and morphological identification of benthic taxa. However, recent advancements in environmental DNA (eDNA) techniques for monitoring the diversity of benthic communities or the abundance of specific indicator taxa from sediment or filtered water samples are revolutionizing aquatic biomonitoring (Deiner et al., 2017; Pawlowski et al., 2022; Power et al., 2023; Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015). The exponential growth of eDNA-based techniques such as real-time qPCR, digital PCR, metabarcoding and metagenomics has been driven by technological advancements that have significantly reduced sequencing costs (Tsuji et al., 2019). This coupled with the increased accessibility to biotechnological laboratory facilities (e.g., Next-generation sequencing (NGS) platforms, bioinformatics pipelines, reference sequence databases) has made these methods more affordable and widely available. The first eukaryotic metabarcoding studies (Fonseca et al. 2010), emphasised the

revolutionary potential of eDNA metabarcoding for assessing diversity levels across various habitats particularly in benthic setting. Building on this, also a decade ago, Bourlat et al. (2013) proposed that genomic technologies would support marine monitoring programs in achieving the goals of marine legislation. These foundational insights have paved the way for the widespread adoption of eDNA-based methods in marine and other environmental monitoring efforts.

Since then, eDNA-based methods have been evaluated and are considered to be routinely implemented in order to complement or replace the spatial mapping and diversity monitoring targeting eukaryotic organisms such as macroinvertebrates, macroalgae, zoo- and phytoplankton or even fish and marine mammals, that were previously monitored using direct observation or microscopy of collected benthos (Thomsen et al., 2016, 2012). Recent years have also seen several studies showcasing the relevance of monitoring the diversity of benthic microorganisms, which can serve as bioindicators of ecosystem impact and other environmental changes (e.g. Aylagas et al., 2014; Cordier et al., 2017; Fonseca et al., 2022, 2014; Keeley et al., 2018; Lanzén et al., 2021b). This generally requires data-driven approaches due to the lack of historical knowledge of the autoecology of specific species. Nonetheless, these methods can provide very accurate results, particularly when monitoring the diversity of microorganisms. The generally more homogenous distribution of microorganisms in the environment allows for more consistent and reliable data collection and analysis compared to monitoring larger organisms. This facilitates a better understanding of ecosystem dynamics and enhances our ability to track changes and trends in biodiversity over time (Cordier et al., 2019). These examples show how eDNA can be used for environmental impact assessment of marine industries and early detection of invasive and/or harmful organisms (see also Aglieri et al., 2023; Fonseca et al., 2023; Grey et al., 2018; Knudsen et al., 2022, Fonseca et al 2023). eDNA-based biodiversity surveys have already been shown to increase detection sensitivity of invasive species (Fonseca et al., 2023; Westgaard et al., 2024), being less selective for different taxonomies, and having better cost-efficiency compared to traditional surveying methods (Rishan et al., 2023), provided the number of samples are sufficiently high (Harper et al., 2018). eDNA approaches in benthic habitats can be used to monitor the presence of migratory and endangered species in critical habitats considering their ecology and reproductive cycles. These methods are particularly useful because some species spend a significant portion of their life cycle in other environments such as *Lamproretra fluviatilis* metamorphosing in estuarine environments. Assessing their presence in such environments using eDNA from sediments, allows gaining insights into the presence and movement of these species, contributing to better conservation and management strategies. This approach provides an efficient and non-invasive way to track and protect vulnerable species during important stages of their life cycle. However, no method, including eDNA-based surveys can identify all taxa in an ecosystem. As proposed by Djurhuus et al. (2020), when using eDNA to survey ecosystems over time, it can reveal ecosystem changes and improve forecasting of biodiversity shifts that may result from environmental changes that occur across time scales and locations helping future efforts for proactive conservation of life in the oceans and beyond. Three critical phases of eDNA-based analyses can be identified: sample collection, laboratory analyses and data analyses. Each phase plays a crucial role in ensuring accurate and reliable results and below each of them are discussed.

Sample collection

Sampling methods vary depending on I) the type of environment (water depth, soft/coarse sediment layers etc.), and II) target organisms. eDNA comprises both DNA that has been shed from larger organisms as well as whole and intact, smaller organisms (such as microorganisms, plankton, etc.) that can be accumulated by filtering water or sampling sediments (Didaskalou et al., 2022; Power et al., 2023). When comparing eDNA sampling from sediment and water, both have their own challenges, but sampling from sediment can be considered more challenging for a few reasons. For example, sediment samples often contain a mixture of organic and inorganic matter, which can complicate eDNA extraction and analysis. The presence of contaminants or inhibitors in sediment samples can further interfere with DNA extraction and amplification (Williams et al., 2017; Pawlowski et al., 2022). The binding of eDNA to sediment particles can pose additional challenges during extraction and processing. Also, sediments can be highly heterogeneous, with variable composition across small spatial scales. This may lead to less consistent and representative samples compared to water, which tend to be more homogenous (Guardiola et al., 2015). Collecting sediment samples can be more physically demanding and requires specialised equipment such as corers or grab samplers and harder to sample in remote deep-sea habitats (Pawlowski et al., 2022). An exception is the collection of sediment samples from intertidal sites. Proper handling and storage of sediment samples are essential to preserve the integrity of the eDNA. Water eDNA sampling, on the other hand, tends to be more straightforward because of the ease of filtering water to capture eDNA and the more uniform distribution of DNA in the water column. However, both sediment and water eDNA sampling require careful planning and execution to obtain accurate and reliable results. eDNA is also successfully extracted from filter feeders' tissue, such as shrimps and marine sponges (Jeunen et al., 2023). In addition, Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) that have stacked PVC plates to provide suitable settlement surfaces for species, can be used to collect organisms for morphological and molecular identification (Thomasdotter et al., 2023), which is especially useful in hard bottom sediments.

Automated sampling of eDNA is at a very early stage of development (Hansen et al., 2020; Hendricks et al., 2023; Thomas et al., 2018), but will, without doubt, become more and more commonly applied, especially if running costs and equipment costs can be decreased. Passive sampling of marine water eDNA is also an approach that is becoming more broadly applied (Bessey et al., 2021). An automatic benthic sampler for hard and mixed bottom substrates has also been developed and tested by Keeley et al. (2021), although this approach remains highly experimental.

Grand sampling setups can include the use of citizen science to help accumulate more water samples than individual researchers can collect and can help monitoring for organisms suspected to inhabit the area sampled (Agersnap et al., 2022; Knudsen et al., 2023; Leerhøi et al., 2024; Miya et al., 2022; Valsecchi et al., 2023).

Just as traditional monitoring is affected by seasonal variation and diurnal shifts in species composition, eDNA levels in aquatic filtered water samples are also influenced by changes over the year (Agersnap et al., 2022; Budd et al., 2023; Sigsgaard et al., 2017), and by diurnal variations in species composition (Jensen et al., 2022). These fluctuations can impact the detection and abundance estimates of species within eDNA samples, making it important to consider the timing of sampling and account for potential changes in species presence and activity patterns when designing studies and interpreting results (Fonseca, 2018). Adjusting for these temporal factors can help improve the accuracy and reliability of eDNA-based monitoring. For example, in Northern Europe during the spring, marine fish like garfish (*Belone belone*) and lumpsucker (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) are active and spawn, resulting in a noticeable increase in their eDNA levels in the water column, which can be detected using eDNA-based methods (Agersnap et al., 2022; Sigsgaard et al., 2017). However, their eDNA levels remain low throughout the rest of the year in the same habitat, reflecting the seasonality of their life cycles and emphasizing the need to account for temporal variation when conducting eDNA studies. After nightfall, eels (*Anguilla anguilla*) and sculpins (*Scorpaeniformes*) become more active than during the day, resulting in higher eDNA levels in the water column reflecting their increased nighttime activity (Jensen et al., 2022). Also, non-indigenous species such as the sea walnut (*Mnemiopsis leydii*) become more abundant in Northern Europe's coastal waters during late summer. This seasonal increase is also evident in higher concentrations of eDNA from these species in the water column (Knudsen et al., 2022).

Taking seasonal and diurnal variations into account is important for optimizing species eDNA monitoring and maximizing the likelihood of detecting target organisms. Species composition in marine coastal habitats also varies across different depths, which is reflected in the eDNA collected at various depths (DiBattista et al., 2019). Adjusting sampling strategies to account for these variations can improve the accuracy and representativeness of eDNA-based assessments. To detect benthic-associated organisms using eDNA, it may be beneficial to sample water near the seabed, as this is where the organisms are most concentrated. On the other hand, Antich et al., (2021) found that 95% of benthic in-fauna species identified using eDNA from marine sediments were not detected when using eDNA from filtered bottom water samples. This further reiterates the importance of selecting appropriate sampling methods and sources to effectively monitor benthic communities. Wind and currents can lead to some mixing of the upper layers of a water column, but counter currents and haloclines can prevent proper mixing and stratify the water seasonally. This advocates for very careful planning when conducting eDNA studies, as random sampling may not provide the comprehensive data required to answer specific research questions. Furthermore, there is growing support that eDNA compositions can vary significantly in water samples collected simultaneously from the very same location (Ficetola et al., 2015; Stauffer et al., 2021). This introduces considerable variation across samples, particularly for rare species, that might shed less eDNA compared to more abundant organisms. Such variability underscores the need for careful sampling strategies and replication to ensure representativeness and reliable eDNA data. This calls for several biological field replicates, which can raise project costs. However, increasing the number of samples may be necessary for detecting rare species, similar to traditional monitoring. The advantages of this approach, including technical DNA extraction replicates, have also been demonstrated

several times in sediment eDNA studies. Replication tends to be more advantageous with increasing organism size for benthic fauna, as larger organisms are expected to have more heterogeneous distributions (Hestetun et al., 2021a, 2021b; Lanzén et al., 2017). The alternative is to increase the volume of sediment from which eDNA is extracted or to use “massive metabarcoding” (Flo et al., 2023; Nascimento et al., 2018); which in some cases might be a valid option when something rare is sought.

Once samples are collected, the eDNA is extracted from the sample and subsequent laboratory analysis is applied to identify which organisms are present in the vicinity of the sampled location (Pawlowski et al., 2020; Taberlet et al., 2012). This process allows to gain insights into local biodiversity and species composition at different taxonomy levels and resolution, depending on the approach and markers used.

Laboratory analyses

The laboratory methodology covers both species-specific detection of DNA (targeted assays), as well as screening of whole communities for specific taxonomic groups by amplifying barcoding gene fragment(s) (metabarcoding approach, Harper et al., (2018)). Additionally, metagenomics shotgun sequencing involves direct sequencing of total eDNA, allowing detailed insights into community composition (Cowart et al., 2018). The choice of approach depends on the specific objectives of the survey or study. Species-specific detection is a quantitative or semi-quantitative method enabling rough estimate of the abundance of the target species in the vicinity of the sampling area (Knudsen et al., 2019; Salter et al., 2019). Targeted assays typically involve quantitative PCR (qPCR), digital PCR (dPCR), or digital droplet PCR (ddPCR). Among these methods, ddPCR have been shown to provide more accurate estimates of eDNA levels in filtered water samples compared to qPCR (e.g., Capo et al., 2021; Zaiko et al., 2022). eDNA metabarcoding, on the other hand, has limitations in terms of preference for amplifying specific taxonomic groups over others, aka ‘primer bias’ (Kelly et al., 2019). This variability can prevent using the quantification of eDNA molecules as a proxy for abundance or biomass. Instead, eDNA metabarcoding serves as a qualitative index of the targeted phylum within the monitoring setup, providing a general indication of presence rather than precise abundance estimates (relative abundances). The metagenomics approach, while highly informative, remains rather costly and is often not the most affordable choice for many of the studies. However, DNA sequencing costs are decreasing, and an alternative strategy is to perform massive metabarcoding to allow capturing rare eDNA sequences that represent rare organisms in the sample providing valuable insights into the presence and diversity of less common species (Flo et al., 2023). Depending on the techniques employed, one can obtain quantitative data (qPCR, dPCR, ddPCR), semiquantitative data and presence/absence data (metabarcoding, metagenomics) targeting both taxonomical and functional biodiversity across all marine biological compartments, from microbes to mammals. These methods can be applied to both pelagic and benthic environments, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of marine biodiversity across different habitats and ecological domains.

Data analyses

Once the raw data are available, the choice of a data analysis pipeline and abundance and similarity thresholds can significantly influence the diversity findings. Different methods, such as clustering and non-clustering approaches, can yield varying results (e.g. Giebner et al., 2020; Porter and Hajibabaei, 2020). The choice of the pipeline could impact the interpretation of biodiversity, making it essential to select the appropriate tools for accurate and reliable analysis.

When conducting taxonomic assignment, incomplete or incorrectly curated reference databases can pose significant challenges for the identification of sequence reads obtained through eDNA metabarcoding. These issues can hinder the development of valid, species-specific eDNA detection assays (Aylagas et al., 2014). The answers that can be obtained from eDNA are only as reliable as the underlying genetic reference databases. Many genetic databases have incorrect identified species associated with sequences deposited (Farrell et al., 2021), other taxonomic groups are species complexes in dire need of a taxonomic revision, which calls for traditional alpha taxonomy and taxonomic revisions carried out alongside of having vouchered material deposited in museum collections. To fully leverage eDNA monitoring tools, it is strongly advised to collaborate with taxonomists or museum collections, that can assess the plausibility of detecting a specific organism and its eDNA at the sampled location. Relying solely on raw results from a bioinformatician can lead to erroneous conclusions about long migrations or the introduction of new species. As with all scientific endeavours, careful and meticulous examination of the eDNA data is essential to ensure accurate interpretations. Nevertheless, taxonomists also face challenges when dealing with cryptic species or developmental larval stages that are difficult to detect with the naked eye.

Several attempts were made to standardize the assessment of marine invertebrate and indicator species (Aylagas et al., 2014) and to compare traditional monitoring of marine benthic invertebrates with monitoring using eDNA tools in a metabarcoding setup. However, this approach faces challenges such as rare species being underrepresented in reference databases, and some species potentially going undetected due to lower primer affinity (e.g., primer bias), leading to varying amplification and detection efficiency across different phyla, potentially skewing results. Modelling eDNA dispersal and decay rates in the different environments can enhance the reliability of this method (Lamb et al., 2022). Despite these challenges, eDNA metabarcoding holds great promises (Harper et al., 2018), provided the costs are covered for broad and frequent sampling. However, bioinformatic approaches must be critically assessed for plausibility to ensure accurate interpretations and conclusions.

Applications

Even though costs associated with eDNA monitoring are relatively high, the methodology makes it possible to evaluate hundreds or thousands of samples, which quickly would become very expensive with conventional monitoring (Rourke et al., 2022). Grand scale studies on monitoring using eDNA tools of thousands of samples are scarce, but the costs per individual sample and hours for handling samples are competitively lower when hundreds of samples are to be analysed (Harper et al., 2018; Sternhagen et al., 2024). eDNA monitoring has

repeatedly demonstrated its ability to detect a broader range of species than traditional monitoring methods (Ramón-Laca et al., 2021; Sigsgaard et al., 2017; Thomsen et al., 2012; Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015). Additionally, it effectively considers temporal and seasonal variations (Castro-Cubillos et al., 2022; Hervé et al., 2022; Saenz-Agudelo et al., 2024), including diurnal changes (Allan et al., 2021; Djurhuus et al., 2020; Jensen et al., 2022).

The proven potential eDNA for monitoring communities and habitats, has led to a significant increase in its application over the past decade (Rourke et al., 2022; Tsuji et al., 2019). Despite this growth, large-scale studies involving thousands of samples are still limited in this field. This may change as autonomous samplers become more widely available and implemented, enabling the efficient processing of thousands of samples (Hansen et al., 2020; Hendricks et al., 2023; Truelove et al., 2022). These advancements could greatly enhance the scope and precision of eDNA-based monitoring.

Demersal and benthic fish species

The movement of both organisms and the eDNA in aquatic environments, can make precise mapping of species distribution challenging. However, conventional monitoring suffers from similar limitations in mapping distribution of organisms. Despite these challenges, eDNA-based monitoring has been readily applied in multiple studies to estimate the distribution of benthic fishes (Knudsen et al., 2019; McCarthy et al., 2023; Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015; Veron et al., 2023). This method has also been used to identify non-indigenous species (Feist and Lance, 2021; Knudsen et al., 2022; Westfall et al., 2022), evaluate species in by-catch (Urban et al., 2024), and monitor eDNA from benthic-associated fish (Maes et al., 2024). Additionally, eDNA-based monitoring has proven effective for deep-sea fish observation (Kawato et al., 2021; Thomsen et al., 2016; Yoshida et al., 2023), including using water samples from within deep-sea sponges (Brodnicke et al., 2023; Harper et al., 2023). Water sampling for eDNA profiling offers a non-invasive method for addressing population genetic questions related to individual genetic variants. In contrast, conventional population genetic research typically requires invasive biopsy sampling (Dugal et al., 2022a; Yoshitake et al., 2021). eDNA-based monitoring of fish has become commonly applied approach, with strong correlations found between species biomass and species-specific eDNA abundance, particularly for species in relation to the extent of their habitat coverage (Salter et al., 2019). Suggesting that future strengths of eDNA-based monitoring may lie in its ability to estimate biomass and map species distributions effectively.

Benthic fauna and microorganisms

Early studies on benthic microfauna have focused more on diversity and studies on monitoring are scarcer. The research that does exist faces challenges due to the a interstitial meiofauna being poorly described taxonomically and misrepresented in genetic reference databases (Gielings et al., 2021). However, a growing number of studies have demonstrated the use of meio- and microfauna to provide accurate assessments of human impact on marine, coastal and estuarine benthic ecosystems (Aylagas et al., 2017; Cordier et al., 2017; Fonseca et al., 2022; Keeley et al., 2018; Lanzén et al., 2021a; Mauffrey et al., 2021). These studies include

taxonomy-free or agnostic methods, supported by numerical analysis or machine learning, which are especially promising for microbenthos (including eukaryotes), since they do not rely on species delineations or prior knowledge about the auto-ecology of specific taxa (reviewed in Cordier et al., 2017).

Using mainly core sampling technique addressing the composition of benthic micro-organisms by DNA profiling has been a research area in focus for decades and has been applied before monitoring of eDNA from macro-organisms in filtered water samples saw an onset of research studies. Monitoring of marine benthic prokaryotes has been conducted alongside eDNA-based monitoring of marine benthic invertebrates, to understand microbial and meiofauna assemblages and diversity patterns in marine habitats (Fonseca et al., 2022; Lo Giudice and Rizzo, 2022). This parallel monitoring approach helps relate benthic prokaryotes communities to ecological habitat differences and assess the impact of human activities, such as oil drilling platforms (Lanzén et al., 2021). Additionally, these studies have explored how benthic prokaryotic communities correlate with geochemical profiles of marine benthic sediments (Jorgensen et al., 2012). Improved bioinformatic approaches (Odom et al., 2023) enable faster assessment and evaluation of diversity and species composition through eDNA-based monitoring from prokaryotes, offering broader coverage of species diversity compared to traditional prokaryote monitoring.

Metabarcoding of eDNA from larger benthic invertebrates, when paired with more frequent and numerous sampling, and optimised in-house or targeted well-curated reference databases, can provide a clearer picture of invertebrate communities compared to conventional monitoring methods (Günther et al., 2022) This approach holds the promise of providing more detailed mapping of biogeographic patterns, allowing to gain a deeper understanding of community structure distribution. Leveraging these advanced techniques allows achieving more comprehensive assessments of marine ecosystems and their biodiversity. However, most routine monitoring studies utilising DNA metabarcoding of macrobenthos rely on homogenates from collected specimens rather than eDNA, which may increase the sequencing of target organisms while reducing the inclusion of eDNA from early life stages or dead or dormant cells, including those from the pelagic. Nonetheless, results generated in this manner, as well as from direct extraction of eDNA from sediments, have been found to align with traditional morphology-based methods when using biotic indices to assess ecosystem status (Aylagas et al., 2018; Lanzén et al., 2021a). Also, metabarcoding of eDNA has the potential for addressing invertebrate community composition in hard-to-reach areas such as polar habitats (Cowart et al., 2018; Fonseca et al., 2022, 2017; Vause et al., 2019).

Seagrass, macroalgae and corals

Marine seagrass habitats are vital for many threatened species and play a crucial role in maintaining healthy marine ecosystems. Despite their significance, monitoring their distribution has not been fully implemented, representing an opportunity for improvement (Unsworth et al., 2022). The lack of a comprehensive genetic reference database for coral species has limited the effectiveness of coral eDNA monitoring, leaving the field in its early stages (Alexander et al., 2020; Dugal et al., 2022b; West et al., 2022). This shortcoming is likely to

persist for some time, as genetic reference databases continue to lack many species or contain incorrectly identified sequences.

Monitoring of eDNA from macroalgae has been linked to carbon deposition in sediment and can vary across different habitats (Graves et al., 2022; Ortega et al., 2020). However, as with corals, eDNA-based monitoring of macroalgae also suffers from inadequate species coverage on genetic reference databases and complex taxonomy that often leads to erroneous classification (Bartolo et al., 2020). Timing water sampling for monitoring macroalgae, seagrass and corals using eDNA with seasonal release of gametes, spores and zygotes can optimize the chances of detection, as the eDNA levels will be higher during this period. Additionally, eDNA will allow for easier detection of hidden or elusive microalgae within a habitat (Bartolo et al., 2020), offering a new perspective on algal diversity that conventional monitoring methods may have been unable to capture (Weng et al., 2024). By establishing robust monitoring practices, we can better track changes in seagrass, macroalgae and corals coverage and health, which is essential for the conservation of these delicate habitats and the species they inhabit. Implementing comprehensive monitoring systems could help inform conservation efforts and guide strategies to protect these threatened marine areas.

In spite of the challenges related to monitoring the diversity or presence of coral, macroalgae or seagrass species themselves, several studies have successfully monitored the microorganisms and macroinvertebrates inhabiting these areas or the commensals and symbionts of these organisms. For example, Bengtsson et al. (2017), Cowart et al. (2015) Mwamburi et al. (2023), Turon et al. (2020), and Waters et al. (2023), have inventoried the diversity of *Zostera* and *Posidonia* spp. seagrass meadows from sediment or commensals of the plants themselves. Other studies have focused on past plant species composition in coastal areas from sediment ancient DNA (Foster et al., 2024), examined the communities associated with coral reefs (e.g. Angly et al., 2016; Bucklin et al., 2011; Djurhuus et al., 2020; Gaidos et al., 2011; Jensen et al., 2012) or have used eDNA to compare the structure of microbial, meio- or macrofauna communities from coral reefs affected by oil spills to unaffected reefs (e.g. DiBattista et al., 2020; Oladi et al., 2022).

With a sufficient number of sample replicates, and a high number of primers set combinations monitoring of eDNA holds the promise of providing more detailed pictures of the species diversity across time and space (Fonseca, 2018; Takahashi et al., 2023).

Technology readiness level

TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment - “Pilot”

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using eDNA methods are relevant for a number of EBV and EOVs and examples are presented in table 18 and 19.

Table 17. EBVs that can be addressed by satellite-based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Genetic composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genetic diversity - Genetic differentiation (number of genetic units and genetic distance) - Inbreeding
Species populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species distributions - Species abundance
Community composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity

Table 18. EOVs that can be addressed by satellite based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOv that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOv. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOv and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOv, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy species diversity 	
Seagrass cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seagrass diversity (species) 	
Hard coral cover and composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coral diversity (species, genera and functional type; and alpha, beta or gamma) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inventories of coral diversity
Fish abundance and distribution		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish diversity indices
Marine turtle, bird and mammal abundance and distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species presence/absence 	

Technology SWOT: eDNA

Strengths	Weaknesses
Non-invasive	Prone to contaminations
Cost-efficient	eDNA degradation and dispersal rate still unknown
Scalable	Incomplete or incorrectly curated genetic reference databases
Under constant development	Cannot identify stages of life history and can be from dead or decaying biological matters

Alternative technique for studying inaccessible ecosystems	DNA amplification prone to primer biases and is affected by inhibitors
Will likely be automated in the future	Difficult to automate
Can detect the presence of organisms from early life stages	
Opportunities	Threats
eDNA Provides a novel source material to monitor biodiversity	Lack of standardised methods
Use of citizen science	If databases are not improving, samples can be assigned only to higher taxonomic levels
Can provide information about the spatial distribution and temporal variability of the species	
Makes possible to conduct comprehensive ecosystem studies	

Biologging

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Method description

Biologging, which involves the utilization of animal-borne sensors or devices, has revolutionised the study of seabird movements, behaviour, physiology, and responses to environmental changes, at various spatial and temporal scales (Fehlmann and King, 2016; Hays et al., 2016; Wilmers et al., 2015; Yoda, 2019). Biologging technologies can be of different types depending on the characteristics of the data collected and multiple technologies/sensors can be installed in the same device to collect multiple types of data at the same time. Although biologging technologies can be used on different organisms (e.g. pop-up satellite archival tags to track demersal fish species), this section exclusively discusses devices for seabirds.

The following is a comprehensive list of existing technologies depending on the aspect of the behaviour, ecology, or environment of the individuals for which the collected information is being used. Regarding individuals' movement: Global Positioning System (GPS) and Geolocation System (GLS) devices are widely used to record positions and track individual movements. Regarding spatial accuracy GPS devices have higher resolution (<5 m) than GLS (>200 km) (Chung et al., 2021). GPS devices determine the animal positions from satellite signals and the information can be obtained via Very High Frequency (VHF), Advanced Research and Global Observation Satellite (Argos) or Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) systems (e.g. Davies et al., 2021). However, GLS devices employ a light-intensity sensor and a precise real-time clock to determine individual locations. This is achieved by calculating the time of solar noon and the length of the day to derive

latitude and longitude, respectively. In the latter case, the devices must be retrieved to obtain the information limiting their use almost exclusively to studies of seabirds in colonies (e.g. Lewin et al., 2024). Furthermore, there are other significant differences, such as data transmission in remote areas, information storage capacity, battery life, and the possibility of recharging. For instance, GPS devices may incorporate solar panels for battery recharging, whereas GLS devices do not have recharging capability. Altimeter attached to tracking devices to measure flight altitude and Time-depth Recorder (TDR) to measure diving depth enabling the study of the use of 3D environment (e.g. Darby et al., 2022a). Wet/dry sensor records periods when the logger is submerged in either fresh or salty water. These data can be used to determine when individuals depart and arrive at the colony depending on whether they are sitting in the nest (dry) or in the sea (wet). Accelerometers measure seabirds' body movements, allowing to infer behaviours such as flight, diving, and feeding (e.g. Kogure et al., 2016). This technique provides valuable data on energy expenditure and activity patterns, complementing tracking devices. However, challenges in data interpretation and calibration exist, particularly for species with complex movement patterns. Magnetometers measure the orientation and navigation of flying seabirds. Magnetometer data provides information about the direction and inclination of the Earth's magnetic field that birds use to orient themselves (Conners et al., 2021). Radio frequency identification (RFID) tags consisting of a microchip containing a unique identification (ID) code and an antenna for communication. The radio signals transmitted, typically through VHF or ultra-high-frequency (UHF) waves, are captured by a RFID reader either when an individual passes near a receiver or when the researcher search for an individual in an area (e.g. Ainley et al., 2006).

As far as foraging behaviour is concerned, there are some specific devices for its study: temperature sensor/transmitter pill to record the temperature inside the lumen of the stomach and of the oesophagus simultaneously as a detector of food intake (Ancel et al., 1997). These devices can only collect data for a few hours, until the individual regurgitates the pill. Beak sensor consisting of a magnet affixed to one mandible, which was used to produce a magnetic field. The strength of this field was detected by a Hall sensor attached to the other mandible and fitted to a logger, which records sensor voltage, proportional to magnetic field strength, and thus inter-mandibular angle used to describe ingestion, breathing, calling, head shaking and preening (Hanuise et al., 2010). Video-camera loggers are primarily used to document the searching and ingesting behaviour of predators and can be used to study the use of visual cues for prey pursuit or general foraging behaviour. These devices consume a significant amount of battery, so their recording capacity typically cannot cover a round trip for foraging (i.e., a basic unit of behaviour during the breeding season) that can last from several hours to days (Yoda, 2019).

Concerning physiological biologging, different devices are available to record different physiological signs such as electrocardiogram, electroencephalogram, body temperature, blood pressure and glucose levels in blood loggers enabling researchers to assess seabirds' stress levels, energy expenditure, and reproductive behaviour. Finally, there are different types of sensors that measure and collect data from environmental parameters such as water temperature, salinity, oxygen concentration, or fluorescence. These sensors can be deployed alongside biologging devices to investigate seabirds' responses to their surroundings offering insights into habitat preferences, foraging behaviour, and the impact of environmental variability on seabird populations.

Finally, regarding the environmental conditions surrounding seabird individuals, video-camera loggers can also be used to see what an individual sees in the field and hear what it hears (Moll et al., 2007). Recently, advancements in technology have led to the development of systems capable of detecting radar transmissions and AIS (Automatic Identification System) transmissions which indicate vessel presence and identification, respectively (Navarro-Herrero et al., 2023).

Figure 5. European shag (*Gulosus aristotelis*) equipped with a GPS-GSM device. Photo credit: Jon Zubiaur.

Applications

Biologging techniques have been widely used to monitor seabirds enabling researchers to study their physiology (Williams and Ponganis, 2021; J. H. Darby et al., 2022b, 2022; Carlsen et al., 2023), track species movements and distributions (Péron and Grémillet, 2013; Clay and Brooke, 2024), foraging strategies (Cook et al., 2017), map the extent and quality of seabird habitats such as nesting sites and foraging grounds (McLeay et al., 2010; Afán et al., 2021), identify hotspots (Fort et al., 2012; Davies et al., 2021b) and assess the effectiveness of conservation measures. In addition, biologging devices have been used for other applied studies such as in the context of marine spatial planning (Augé et al., 2018; Ehler, 2018; Davies et al., 2021a), the assessment of potential fisheries bycatch (Weimerskirch et al., 2018; Clay et al., 2019) or the location of illegal fisheries (Weimerskirch et al., 2020). Biologging, as outlined in the OBAMA-NEXT deliverable 2.1, extends its application beyond seabird species to encompass other marine organisms like fish (e.g., tunas and sharks), squid, octopuses, marine mammals and turtles. This expanded scope underscores the versatility and applicability of biologging technology across various taxa within marine ecosystems.

Technology readiness level

The Technological Readiness Level of biologging for seabirds varies depending on specific devices and technologies. In general, biologging sensors and devices for seabirds have reached a high TRL 8-9, with many

devices proven in operational environment and being widely used in research and conservation management. However, even if the TRL is already high, advances and refinements of certain sensors continue to be made probably raising their TRL in a near future, improving their effectiveness under various conditions.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using data gathered by biologging are relevant for a number of EBVs and EOVs and examples are presented in table 20 and 21.

Table 19. EBVs that can be addressed by satellite based technologies, as defined by the GEOBON

(<https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

EBV class	EBV name
Species populations	- Species distributions
Species traits	- Physiology - Movement - Reproduction

Table 20. EOVs that can be addressed by satellite based technologies. Sub-variables: Components of the EOV that may be measured, derived or inferred from other elements of the observing system and used to estimate the desired EOV. Derived products: Outputs calculated from the EOV and other relevant information, in response to user needs. For each EOV, a specification sheet can be downloaded from <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>.

EOV name	Sub-variables	Derived products
Fish abundance and distribution		
Marine turtle, bird and mammal abundance and distribution	- Repeated individual presence (tracking/resights)	- Home range - Utilization distribution (relative occupation of home range) - Movement patterns - Migration pathways - Habitat maps

Technology SWOT: Biologging

Strengths	Weaknesses
Integration of multiple sensors (e.g., GPS, accelerometers, depth, ambient temperature, radar detector sensors) in the same device	Transmitted data is constrained by the satellite system message size and it is necessary to retrieve the devices
Data precision: real-time and/or high-resolution data which provide priceless insights into otherwise largely inaccessible biological systems	Battery size may pose problems concerning its suitability for use with small species and

	potentially disrupt their natural movement patterns
Some devices enable long-term monitoring periods, allowing for comprehensive studies of seabird ecology	GPS devices cannot be used to track animals underwater (position must be inferred from depth and accelerometer data)
Individuals could serve as “oceanographers” for sampling environmental data in regions not covered by survey networks or in habitats where traditional measurement methods prove inadequate	Complex interpretation of raw data which analytically requires high degree of technical skills
Eliminate the need for direct observation, facilitating data collection in remote or inaccessible locations	Devices may experience technical malfunctions, loss, or premature detachment, resulting in incomplete or lost data sets
Opportunities	Threats
Advancements in tagging technology enhance data accuracy, battery life, and the range of measurable parameters	Animal welfare, legal and ethical concerns
Integration with satellite telemetry, remote sensing, and environmental sensors enhances the scope and depth of seabird and their environment research	Tagged devices might increase the energy expenditure associated with swimming/flying and potentially modify the behaviour of animals
Outreach initiatives based on biologging can raise public awareness about seabird ecology and conservation issues	Colourful loggers may alter interaction dynamics with conspecifics/heterospecifics

Citizen Science

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Method description

Although a clear definition is still lacking, Citizen Science (CS) is typically intended as research activities conducted by (non-expert) citizens or engaging citizens (at different levels and to a different degree) – as data collectors, co-analysts, co-researcher or policy co-developers – to deliver scientific knowledge inspired by the principles of co-creation, co-operation, sustainability and/or social impact (see Hecker et al., 2018; Jaeger et al., 2023; Kasperowski and Kullenberg, 2019, 2019; Strasser et al., 2019; Vohland et al., 2021). Also, CS is used as an ‘umbrella’ term to describe a variety of ways in which citizens can participate to scientific activities leading to scientific knowledge production; namely, the concept is related to other notions such as *participatory science*, *post-normal science*, *civic science*, *crowd science* or *open science* (Kieslinger et al., 2018; Kullenberg and Kasperowski, 2016). The characteristics of CS are: (1) citizens are actively involved in research, in partnership or collaboration with scientists or academic professionals; and (2) there is a specific outcome such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy changes. An international community of researchers and practitioners

led by the *European Citizen Science Association* (ECSA) has characterised CS and established the standards for good CS practices in several disciplines (see Haklay et al., 2021, 2020; Robinson et al., 2018). These efforts gave origin to a framework of ten principles ([10 Principles of Citizen Science – ECSA 2015](#)), available in several languages, where the CS community established a set of distinctive characteristics for “good” CS practices.

The latest debate on CS evolved from its historical roots (Bonney, 1996; Irwin, 2002) to identify instead, which projects, scientific activities or initiatives constitute CS, so that CS could be easily distinguished by other forms of participatory research. What seems foundational for CS is the participatory stance, further expressed by the degree of non-expert, citizen engagement in higher-level scientific tasks (see Haklay et al., 2021, 2020). Following Golumbic et al. (2017), three fundamental aspects of CS are: a) inclusion (i.e., how researchers deal with activities built for public participation); b) contribution (i.e., how a project contributes to science, and at the same time, how it impacts the public) and, c) reciprocity (i.e., what citizens and researchers can do for each other in the context of knowledge elicitation and dissemination). Similarly, existing scales to evaluate CS projects by Bonney et al. (2009a, 2009b, 2016) point to the degree of citizen contribution to research results and so, CS studies are defined as being either merely contributory (i.e., research questions and/or protocols are established by powerful researchers, institutional promoters and the like with little or no inputs by citizens) or genuinely collaborative (i.e., the citizen involvement in the creation of the project and its protocols is significant and established via genuine collaborations amongst citizens and researchers institutional promoters). Similarly, Haklay (2013a, 2013b) outline a 4-levels scale of citizen involvement, where research activities to be called CS should imply voluntary participation at all levels: from level one (Crowdsourcing: citizens act mainly as sensors) moving up to level two (Distributed Intelligence: citizens act as basic interpreters) and level three (Participatory Science: citizens participate in the problem/aims definition and/or data collection), until the level four (Extreme CS), where citizens partake in all tasks involved at previous levels (1-2-3), those took place almost simultaneously. Also, Haklay et al. (2021, 2020) indicate additional specifications required to classify CS projects across fields (level of cognitive engagement, professionalism and training required for participants, conditions for data/results sharing). Therefore, the main challenge in marine biology and biodiversity (MBB) (as in any other field) will be to figure out if, how and to what extent the participatory ideal entailed by CS is fulfilled by (self-defined) CS studies; namely, due to realistic limitations that non-expert citizens can encounter to actively participate in research and observational tasks in marine environments.

Overall, there seems to be a growing interest for CS in MBB and related areas. Within the environmental and ecological sciences, non-professional participants increasingly contribute to data collection (contributory CS) (Fraisl et al., 2022). Indeed, CS is considered a valuable practice in situations where data are lacking or temporally and spatially insufficient or funding is sparse (Andrews et al., 2019; Callaghan et al., 2021; Garcia-Soto et al., 2021). Citizens can make observations at several locations simultaneously and collect data that may not otherwise be possible to obtain (Matear et al., 2019). Yet, the potential of CS in marine biodiversity studies seems not fully explored because it primarily focuses on specific species’ distribution while neglecting the

other broader aspects of biodiversity, e.g., ecosystem services (Chandler et al., 2017; Derville et al., 2018; Embling et al., 2015; Mannino and Balistreri, 2018; Turbé et al., 2019; Wege et al., 2020). Citizens involved are depicted as primarily motivated by the social network, level of enjoyment, the feeling of contributing to something, and participating in a project with minimal effort (Dalby et al., 2021). Still, little work on CS is done in the more subjective and personal frame of participation, inclusivity, motivation and barriers, and the work is more focused on data collection/data output, rather than what brings the data output (Dalby et al., 2021). A way to enclose these concerns could be allowing citizens to contribute to the project with the potential to discover the interesting or unexpected, and not just be viewed as a tool for data collection (Lukyanenko et al., 2016). Further, specific to biodiversity, there is a lack of “marine CS” projects compared to the terrestrial environment, and the current approach to the marine is limited to specific groups and approaches (Dalby et al., 2021; Fulton et al., 2019; Garcia-Soto et al., 2021).

Applications

Self-labelled CS studies/initiatives in MBB were identified by conducting a SCOPUS survey on CS studies/initiatives in MBB (between 2013 and October 2023), which the main findings on applications in the field are reported, and the technologies/tools for CS used by “citizen scientists” in observational tasks in benthic/pelagic environments are mapped.

Over more than 1000 papers on general CS, this report findings refer to 76 papers: 42 on tools for CS in benthic observations, 21 on CS tools for pelagic observation and 13 cannot be classified as either benthic or pelagic that can be used for both tasks. Evidently, there is a steady growth in the number of articles published per year in MBB focusing on research conducted under the label of CS initiatives that might underscore a burgeoning enthusiasm within the scientific community of reference (marine biologists) for collaborative, community-driven research endeavours led by both academic scientists and “citizen scientists”. By rigorous peer-reviewed scrutiny, the academic community of marine biologists contributed to re-shaping theoretical frameworks, principles and ethical considerations underpinning CS research in the field. Thus, our results should be taken into careful consideration since they can depict the nature and scope of the CS ideal in MBB and what scientific practices applies to CS studies in the field. What clearly emerge from our survey is that tools/technologies used for CS in different observational tasks in either benthic or pelagic settings are pretty much the same (irrespective of tasks involved). Yet, while in benthic observations, likely due to the characteristics of the research setting, primacy seems given to cameras/imaging tools (e.g., scuba diving techniques requiring expert scuba divers), in pelagic observations *seasonal surveys* and *metadata repositories* are also important (unless cameras/imaging tools are widely used too). Thus, the inclusion of non-expert citizens, a determining factor of CS in other fields, seems more challenging in the benthic than in the pelagic environment. In the 42 papers on tools/technologies used in CS initiatives for benthic observations, the most represented tools/technologies belong to the broad category of imaging/cameras (n=23), since many initiatives ask volunteers to contribute by taking pictures of various elements (fauna, algae, fishes etc.) and upload these pictures in (dedicated) online repositories/digital platforms. To simplify the understanding of technological tools (internal variations), if any camera (different models and

types) was used to produce pictures, we reported the general term “camera”, to later enclose any tools that fit such use-case in the general category “imaging”. In lesser extent, surveys (n=8), laboratory techniques (n=4), online tools and sampling (n=2) but custom and standard tools (n=1), satellites (n=1) and multiple techniques (n=1) are also used in benthic CS.

The latest CS studies in MBB (e.g., Brodie et al., 2023; Graba-Landry et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2023; Vázquez-Delfín et al., 2024) examine/stress the potential of CS for large-scale, monitoring of ecological environments and marine ecosystems, and increasing ocean literacy. Whereas the ability of CS initiatives for collecting data on species at their range edges is known (Robinson et al., 2018), these studies highlight areas where CS projects developments (via better identification of resources, training programs for dedicated volunteers) can enhance data quality and quantity or raise awareness of the ecological importance of understudied habitats. Similarly, CS is seen as a potential tool for monitoring and conserving marine ecosystems, particularly in the case of shallow nearshore habitats (however, limited understanding exists as to the effectiveness of CS programs in engaging the general public or their capacity to collect marine big data, see Dalby et al., 2021). CS programs are often seen as effective methods to collect large volumes of data to assist researchers in monitoring ecological environments: as species shift in their distributions globally, e.g., due to climate change, the use of CS data to detect these shifts is steadily increasing. Most of the 42 survey papers on benthic observations address monitoring or mapping species (seagrass, benthic fauna, demersal fishes) via CS initiatives across the globe (Europe, Australia, South America, Middle East etc.), e.g., for monitoring (García-Gómez et al., 2021, Lee et al., 2023, Mangelli et al., 2021), and for mapping (Mannino et al., 2021, Graba-Landry et al. 2023, and Pottie et al. 2021).

To conclude, the current *status* of CS in MBB can be described as (partly) belonging to CS Levels 1-3 (see Haklay’s taxonomy (2013a, 2013b): citizens are mainly data gatherers/collectors and their role beyond such tasks is not well documented. Activities involving “citizen scientists” beyond data gathering/data collection are poorly described (or not described at all) while fundamental information about their expertise or level/s of intellectual engagement, key standards for CS in other fields, are not specified (but exceptions are founded in later studies e.g., Brodie et al., 2023; Vázquez-Delfín et al., 2024). Another peculiarity of CS in MBB is that it is regularly carried out by non-academic experts while the engagement of non-expert citizens (crucial requirement for CS in other fields) seems more challenging. Namely, participants are (volunteers) expert divers or even retired scientists, which is somewhat expected considering the need of specific expertise to access the benthic and pelagic environments and/or to perform certain scientific undertakings (e.g., eDNA sampling is often associated to CS). Nonetheless, more detailed descriptions of participants in CS projects/studies would highly be desirable to better understand and evaluate which principles or standards of CS are fulfilled by actual scientific practices in MBB and similarly, to figure out how CS practices could be improved (toward classical definition of CS by ECSA or later refinements by Haklay et al., 2021, 2020). Finally, although pivotal importance should be given to the extent of involvement of lay citizens, in MBB the term citizen scientist might be understood broadly to include non-academic experts as well. Similarly, greater attention should be devoted to

tools/technologies (automated and non-automated) used by citizen scientists in their tasks, so that also the readiness level (TRL) of technologies used might better be assessed. The inclusion of these two elements when assessing CS in MBB, we intend, would give a better account of current scientific practices characterised as CS in the field as well as they can help in identifying areas where CS might be promoted, or further implemented to complement investigations and data collection carried out by way of other methodologies.

One example of a CS campaign is the collection of *Fucus* sp. occurrences by the *Finnish Environment Institute* (Syke). *Fucus* (bladderwrack) is a macroalgae and an important habitat-forming species in the Baltic Sea (Figure 6). Syke is collecting occurrence data through the CitObs platform ([link](#), page in Finnish). The observers are asked to pinpoint the location on the map, assess the abundance of the species on a four-tier scale and they can provide a comment and a link to a photo or webpage (uploading images is not possible). Following current CS standards (e.g., Haklay's taxonomies), such practices seem more like crowdsourcing of data gathering. The *Fucus* observation campaign is active on the CitObs platform but the possibility to participate is currently not actively promoted and the data collected has not yet been systematically used in, e.g., assessments.

Figure 6. *Fucus vesiculosus* from the Archipelago Sea in Finland. Photo credits: Juuso Haapaniemi / Parks and Wildlife Finland.

Technology readiness level

Citizen science is not per se a technology, and as such TRL is not something generally reported. The technologies and platforms used within citizen science efforts can be assigned and many examples of completed operational platforms exist (TRL 9), with one prominent example being iNaturalist. Growing levels of automation

are observed in recent studies, but TRL assessments for the different technological tools used by “citizen scientists” (in both areas) are not usually discussed in the papers. This omission can be explained by the fact that CS itself is not a technology (but a general research approach) and CS practices are not univocally related to specific technologies. Yet, in benthic MBB, there seems to be a wide agreement in the community of marine biologists regarding the tools that can be used by “citizen scientists” in specific undertakings (mainly, data collection, data gathering). Likely due to the setting and tasks involved, the focus is on specific tools/technologies, those are directly associated to CS (something not common to CS in other fields). There is, indeed, an impressive similarity on the technologies used in MBB studies in rather different contexts (the same tools are used in Australia, Europe, Asia, South America etc.). Informal discussions on the findings of our survey within the OBAMA-NEXT project’s work packages (WP2, WP3 and WP6) also confirmed this trend.

EBVs and EOVs

Data products derived using citizen science approaches are relevant for all EBVs as citizen science can be used in combination with almost any technology, as long as CS is fostered by offering the citizen scientists training and support to carry out specific scientific tasks (e.g., taking genetic samples) or use some technical tool (e.g., drones) in a certain way. As such, the list includes variables from the classes: genetic composition, species populations, species traits, community composition, ecosystem functioning and ecosystem structure. Benthic or bird related EOVs include fish abundance and distribution, macroalgal canopy cover and composition, seagrass cover and composition, hard coral cover and composition as well as mangrove cover and composition, marine (turtles), birds, (mammals) abundance and distribution.

Technology SWOT: Citizen Science

Strengths	Weaknesses
Low-cost	Misconceptions/bias due to lack of specific expertise of citizen scientists (mitigation actions: provide training)
Fill gaps/caveat in data obtained via other techniques/methods	CS is not a technology itself so, TRL would need to be assessed for every tool/technology used by “citizen scientists” in their tasks
Citizen scientists can make observations at several locations simultaneously and collect data that may not otherwise be obtained	
Opportunities	Threats
Extend CS activities/involvement of citizen scientists to other scientific tasks (beyond data collection, and towards “extreme” forms of CS)	Collection/interpretation biases due to lack of specific expertise of citizen scientists (mitigation actions: genuine collaboration between academic experts and citizen scientists)
Create public awareness on critical marine biodiversity issues specific for benthic/pelagic environments	It is unclear how TRL for tools used for CS might be assessed and by whom: - by expert/non-expert citizen scientists?

	- by researchers/scientists based on data quality? or who else?
Increase ocean literacy	

Conclusions and summary

The catalogue on emerging technologies for benthic mapping contains descriptions of technologies and methods that can be used for monitoring and mapping of benthic habitats and biodiversity divided into ten sections; satellites, drones and aerial platforms, ROVs and AUVs, moorings cabled observatories, and landers, FCM and FIM, imaging by photogrammetry and drop videos, acoustics, eDNA, biologging and citizen science. As the main methods used for the observation of benthic biodiversity using ROVs and AUVs, moorings, cabled observatories, and landers are based on optical methods, these and the imaging by photogrammetry and drop videos sections have been combined into one section for the discussion called *benthic imaging*.

The technologies operate on a range of spatial scales with the ones such as satellite-based observations capturing large spatial extent, but often on behalf of a low taxonomic and spatial resolution, in many cases capturing only habitat level (Table 4). At the other end of the taxonomic range, we have monitoring using eDNA methods which is a promising emerging technology with the potential for observations at a high taxonomic resolution defining the community composition.

Table 21. The table showing the level of data collected by the different methods including highest spatial accuracy (1 = mm-cm, 2 = cm-m, 3 = m-km), spatial extent (1 = local, 2 = regional, 3 = global), current temporal resolution of existing data from technology (1 = one point, 2 = annual time series or short term continues observations, 3 = continues observations), automation potential (1 = no part easy to automate, 2 = data processing or collection has potential for automation, 3 = both collection and processing of data can be automated to a large extent).

Technology	Spatial accuracy	Spatial extent	Temporal resolution	Automation potential
Satellites	2	3	3	3
Drones and aerial platforms	1	2	2	3
Benthic imaging	1	2	2	3
FCM and FIM	2	1	1	1
Acoustics	2	2	2	3
eDNA	3	2	1	2
Biologging	2	3	3	2
Citizen science	2	3	3	3

The type of information products that can be derived using the technologies depend on the spatiotemporal resolution of the observations. Most of the methods can be used to make spatial representations of habitats and species distributions using various data analysis tools including various modelling, methods including both conventional statistical methods, and AI/ML techniques. Methods especially suitable for this purpose include those that cover broad areas with high spatial resolution such as satellites, flying drones (UAVs) and other aerial platforms, biologging devices as well as acoustics. They all, however, require some form of calibration against ground truth data during the development and establishing phase to ensure high quality output data, which can be achieved through carefully designed data validation protocols, such as proposed for drones in Kvile et al. (2024). Other methods such as benthic imaging deployed on various platforms, including observations gathered as part of citizen science efforts, can also be used for spatial modelling if high enough number of observations exist. Recent advances have also been made on using multiple sources of data together, including data produced by monitoring with eDNA tools. Out of the 18 information products under development within OBAMA-NEXT (Borja et al., 2023), 11 are related to some extent to the benthic environment, and ten of them mention spatial maps or allude to spatial products.

Satellite-based mapping is used to quantify and monitor various habitats at large scales such as coral reefs, seagrasses, and macroalgae. The benefits of the technology are the large areal coverage, with free data sources available (from public programs), which supports the development of cost-effective monitoring and the possibility to track change over multiple years. However, satellites are mostly limited to the classification of broader habitat types due to the coarse spatial resolution, and in the marine environment, the optical properties of the water limit the depth that habitats can be mapped. Challenges besides separating spectrally similar species relate to handling of data loads and automation of data processing to final mapping products. Fewer satellites currently have hyperspectral instruments, but as their coverage and the amount of data increase, these are also expected to be used for benthic monitoring increasingly in the coming years.

Similarly, flying drone mapping can provide full cover maps but with a higher spatial and spectral resolution than satellites, at account of spatial coverage. In contrast to satellites, drones have the benefit of targeting smaller scale and more complex habitats, and can be developed to assess habitat classification at species level. In addition, drones provide highly valuable platforms for counting birds and marine mammals and thus support studies of population dynamics. Drone operations can be carried out at a high level of automation with good potential for repeated cost-effective monitoring of sites. However, they are sensitive to weather conditions, local and national legislation, as other optical techniques to the water column optical properties (transparency).

Active acoustic methods have a long history of use within fisheries sciences and for mapping of bathymetry and substrate. Current applications include mapping of cold coral habitats, seagrass beds, macroalgal canopies, shellfish beds and the distribution of fish. Acoustics provide a continuous, fast and non-destructive way of collecting data. The technology is expensive, which can be a limitation. The technology produces vast amounts of backscatter data and future challenges relate to the processing of these data. As opposed to satellites and

drones that also cover large areas, acoustic methods can target deeper depths and would as such be ideal to use jointly with those technologies for full cover mapping of habitats.

Platforms such as moorings, cabled observatories, landers, AUVs, and ROVs are flexible for data collection, as they enable deployment of a variety of sensors such as imaging equipment, eDNA sampling, acoustics such as side scan sonars etc. The methods enable targeted mapping of habitats with fine control by the operator or long-term data collection at a specific location. Many components are easily available, and they allow for wide customisation opportunities. Many of these platforms are useful for targeting deeper areas of several kilometres. For some of the methods positioning under water remains challenging. This is also the case for imaging equipment deployed from boats or operated by divers. Platforms are useful for fostering multidisciplinary studies and enable the collection of multiple types of data simultaneously.

Many of the methods gather optical information, in forms such as spectral information or RGB images. The data can be gathered by satellites, drones, or a variety of underwater platforms. Images can also be gathered by deploying cameras from a boat, by a diver, or when processing samples in the lab using flow through imaging microscopy. Regardless of the source, the handling of the data streams and the processing of the data to usable end products require suitable software, capacity for data storage and processing. Future challenges also include selecting the most suitable processing approaches including statistical modelling, machine learning and AI-methods. A roadmap on linking technical solutions to user need is offered in the OBAMA-NEXT deliverable 4.1 by Fernandes-Salvador et al. (2024).

The onset of biodiversity monitoring by examining DNA in the water has not only resulted in that more locations and organisms can be monitored more easily and more quickly, but has also allowed for a completely new perspective of what inhabits the environments we monitor. Traditional fisheries surveys are often more focused on commercial species, and are hard to perform in coastal waters, and fast swimming fish can evade a trawl and might otherwise only be monitored in ROV or similar. Because of this conventional monitoring can risk end up providing a very one-eyed view on the species composition in the habitats we monitor. Monitoring using eDNA tools can help broaden the scope of what species are present. The drawback is that it is more challenging to constrain the spatial accuracy of the results and pinpoint the exact timing of the occurrence, especially when based on water samples. Still, the organisms detected by eDNA give a different view on regional biodiversity than what usually would be inferred by conventional monitoring, and the species richness inferred by eDNA tools surpasses what can be surveyed by traditional approaches, and although conventional monitoring have been the baseline for many decades for assessing and understanding ecosystems and biodiversity, it might not necessarily be the single overarching truth about what lives in the habitats and regions we monitor.

On the other end of the technology spectrum, we have biologging which offer us very detailed information on individual species. Biologging offers valuable insights into biological systems, particularly when integrated with other research methods (e.g. complement results from eDNA analysis), although challenges such as cost and variation between subjects persist. Despite occasional technical limitations regarding the development of the devices, e.g., making loggers small enough to not affect species movement, biologging facilitates the

collection of detailed data at a fine scale, enabling the comprehensive exploration, testing, and enhancement of our understanding of ecological processes.

Citizen science has many benefits related to public outreach, such as increasing awareness of environmental issues and improving ocean literacy. Many current monitoring campaigns already today rely heavily on the support from citizen scientists reporting their observations. More recently, citizen science ventures have included increasingly sophisticated schemes where almost any technology can be applied and encouraged if the effort is fostered by offering the citizen scientists training and support to carry out specific scientific tasks (e.g. taking genetic samples) or use some technical tool (e.g., drones) in a certain way.

Emerging and existing technologies provide many benefits for monitoring and mapping. Many of them enable long-term continuous monitoring and are cost efficient compared to traditional environmental monitoring techniques. Additionally, many of the technologies offer non-invasive, non-destructive sampling of the environment. Many of the technologies described here can benefit from further developments in the use of AI, machine learning, cloud computing and better processing power available in the future. As both the technologies themselves as well as the data processing steps required develop, the level of technical and specialised skills needed to carry out the monitoring analysis and processing increase. This is a common challenge for all the methods.

To achieve holistic monitoring and mapping of marine benthic habitats using many complementary methods is necessary and future efforts should be put into efficient co-use of methods. Combination of several methods for assessing species diversity and distribution as well as employing frequent and broad covering monitoring is the best approach to get a full comprehension of habitats and ecosystems.

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